

FNS - Cloud

Food Nutrition Security

Food Nutrition Security Cloud

Deliverable 4.1

Food Traceability & Metrology Search Engine

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Table of Contents

1	A traceability search engine as data integration solution	4
2	General design	5
3	Supply chain analysis.....	7
3.1	Olive Oil	7
3.2	Milk.....	10
3.3	Fishery products	12
3.3.1	Common aspects	12
3.3.2	Peculiarities for Atlantic salmon.....	14
3.3.3	Peculiarities for the common sole.....	15
3.3.4	Peculiarities for European anchovy.....	15
3.4	Monitoring of parameters of interest and parameters of influence	16
4	Search engine concept.....	19
5	How to Use the App	25
6	Conclusion	29
7	Appendix	30

1 A traceability search engine as data integration solution

The aim of this deliverable was to develop a search engine concept and a first version as a solution for data integration along different food chains. Such a search engine will be realised as an open-source tool that allows, based on a research query, discovery, access, integration, and analysis of data and metadata describing nutritional quality, food safety, authenticity, and transparency of available food data. Users of such a search engine range from laypersons to experts, from researcher to primary producers, processors, distributors and retailers, from inspection and control agencies to certification bodies, and policymakers (Figure 33). As an example, researchers might wish for access to data useful for modelling purposes and comparative studies. Food businesses might access the tool to visualise parameters and examine stages they are interested in for monitoring or otherwise minimise, for example, nutritional quality losses, or safety issues.

Figure 1. Interoperability network through food system (Palocci and Zoani, 2020).

At a further stage of development, the search engine could also be fed directly with new user data, e.g., datasets collected during research and development activities, or monitoring data from a specific production line. These contributions can be made autonomous (e.g., using IoT) and data may be saved in a blockchain (i.e., tamper-proof).

The search engine represents a tool to support transparency along supply chains, providing citizens with information about products including quality, safety, and authenticity as well as identifying steps along the supply chain with importance for them (e.g., source [organic], suppliers [local]). Scope of information made available can be tailored to the type of user and, for more advanced users, different or more specific data can be presented, as selected by the individual.

2 General design

The traceability search engine concept was designed based on three model food supply chains. Differences amongst the supply chains were considered to avoid similarities and ensure the concept was potential valid for all food chains.

Olive oil, milk, and fish products were selected, based on inclusion of products with:

- a. Both vegetable (olive oil) and animal origins (milk and fish products)
- b. Economic interest from various European geographical areas (e.g., Mediterranean area - olive oil, central Europe - milk, Northern and Mediterranean area - fishery products)
- c. Different supply chains that cover a range of issues and research questions, such as nutrition claims (olive oil), definition of geographical areas (milk and fishery products) and botanical origin with the chain (olive oil), and production sustainability (fishery products)
- d. Potential to extend the case study to include products arising from further processing (e.g., dairy products)

For olive oil, processes leading to edible virgin olive oils (i.e., extra virgin and virgin olive oil), as defined in Reg. (EU) 1308/2013 (cons. 2020), were included. For milk, cows' milk was considered without including dairy products (e.g., cheese). For fishery products, all seawater or freshwater fish and seafood were included except bivalve molluscs, live echinoderms, live tunicates and live marine gastropods, and mammals, reptiles, and frogs, irrespective of whether they were wild or farmed, and all edible forms, parts, and products were included, as defined in Reg. (EC) 853/2004 (cons. 2021). Consequently, to cover the different types of fishery products, three supply chains were examined, namely:

- Atlantic salmon (*Salmon salar*)
- Common sole (*Solea solea*)
- European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*)

Each step in the supply chain, with all possible routes, was mapped from primary production to human intake. Mapping was reported in flowcharts to make the supply chains easier to understand and support analysis and visualisation (see Annexes 1A, 2A, 3A, 3.1A, 3.2A, 3.3A). Subsequently, a table was created where each step was described in detail and inputs and outputs identified. Inputs and outputs described the status of foods entering and exiting, allowing them to be identified specifically (Annexes 1B, 2B, 3B, 3.1B, 3.2B, 3.3B). Where applicable, terms were reported with their official definitions (e.g., FAO, WHO, European Regulations, EFSA documents) (Annexes 1C.1, 1C.2, 2C.1, 2C.2, 3C). Finally, every step was examined to understand how it affects nutritional quality, safety, authenticity, and transparency, and build a catalogue of significant parameters (Annexes 1D, 2D, 3.1C, 3.2C, 3.3C). For nutritional quality, intrinsic attributes of foods, such as chemical compositions, physical structures, biochemical changes during processing, nutritional values, and nutraceuticals potential (i.e., associations with benefits to human health) were considered as well as shelf-life and ways in which packaging interacted with the foods. For food safety, microbial and chemical contaminations were considered (e.g., hazards from pathogens, microbial spoilage, mycotoxins, metals, pesticides, etc.). Conditions and practices that influence nutritional quality of intrinsic attributes and/ or influence food safety (i.e., leading to contamination or increased risk of foodborne illness) were examined. Authenticity and transparency were based upon chemical or genetic markers and profiles that allowed demonstration of geographical, botanical, or zoological origins, or identification of potential food frauds.

Parameters of (1) interest and (2) influence were identified for each criterion (nutritional quality, safety, authenticity, and transparency) and each step. Parameters of interest (i.e., data) are analytes (e.g., chemical, physical, microbiological substances or components) or proprieties/characteristics (e.g., profile or taste), which might be subject to change(s) depending on conditions under investigation. Parameters of interest were reported for each step or, in some cases, pooled for multiple steps with specification of the matrix (e.g.,

raw materials, semi-finished or finished products). Some are provided by the manufacturers, whilst others are measured and declared on a voluntary basis.

Parameters of influence (i.e., metadata) are conditions that can influence or modify parameters of interest. They can refer to the matrix of corresponding stages, or to other aspects (e.g., environmental, processes, conditions). For example, physical-chemical characteristics of soil can influence bio-availabilities of toxic and potentially toxic elements and, therefore, compositions and contents; pedoclimatic conditions, such as temperature, rainfall, and distance from sea, can affect isotope ratios of light elements such as H, C and O and nitrogen level as well as sun exposure, which can affect polyphenols contents.

Finally, for each parameter (or class of parameters) and each step, monitoring systems (e.g., measurement devices) were mapped, differentiating between those for offline detection (e.g., analytic laboratory methodologies) and those permitting in situ and in-line monitoring (e.g., IoT sensors). Based on this, a concept for the traceability search engine was created that allowed searches for different aspects, as described above. This concept is presented in Section 3 and 4.

3 Supply chain analysis

In this section, detailed examinations of the three food chains are summarised and include information about production steps as well as the parameters of interest and influence.

3.1 Olive Oil

Olive oil is a vegetable origin food of high interest to the Mediterranean area. The olive tree, *Olea Europea* (L.), is one of the oldest known cultivated trees in the world. It is widely cultivated in southern Europe and this region accounts for almost 98% of olive oil and table olives production worldwide (Boskou, 2006) with Spain, Italy, and Greece leading production. Olive oil is the major edible oil in Mediterranean countries but is also popular among consumers globally.

Inclusion in the search engine development as a model system allows consideration of multiple research questions, including health claims but also traceability and food frauds. There are several health claims associated with olive oils; the most important is the antioxidant activities of polyphenols, given a positive opinion by EFSA in 2011 (EFSA, 2011) and authorised by the Reg. (EU) 432/2012 (cons. 2021), provided oil contains at least 5 mg of hydroxytyrosol and its derivatives (e.g. oleuropein complex and tyrosol) are present per 20 g of olive oil. However, extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) is vulnerable to frauds because of the ease with which it can be modified and the difficulty in identifying manipulations. The most frequent frauds are blending with other less valuable vegetable oils and replacement with other vegetable oils or olive oils of lower commodity category (e.g., virgin oil sold for extra virgin). Several markers (e.g., isotopic ratio of light and heavier elements, genomic profiles) can be measured to identify botanical origin, focusing on the variety of olives used or their geographical origins. However, the compositions of olive oils are complex as a result of interactions among olive varieties, environmental conditions, fruit ripening, and oil extraction technologies.

The route from cultivation to the oil consumption is depicted in Annex 1A, while the module with specific definitions, and inputs and outputs of each step, is reported in Annex 1B. Lampante oil (LOO) was not considered because is inedible. There are multiple outputs from the separation steps, e.g., pressing splits the olive paste into olive must and olive pomace, and the final centrifugation separates virgin olive oil from the oily deposit. Some steps can also impact sustainability, such subsequent usage of processing by-products (e.g., olive-vegetation water, leaves, kernel, olive pomace). Vegetation water is mainly a wastewater, due to its high content of organic matter, but it contains minerals (e.g., potassium) that are potentially of interest for further utilisation. In Italy, currently, almost all vegetation water is used in controlled spreading on agricultural land (Di Giovacchino, 2013). Olive pomace, the residue from pressing, contains oil that can be extracted using solvent and exhausted olive pomace is used as fuel (caloric value = 3500 kcal/ kg), fertiliser, in animal feed, or mixed into clay for the brick industry. Olive milling can follow multiple processing routes (see Annex 1C.1), resulting in five types of edible oils: 1) EVOO, 2) VOO, 3) refined olive oil, 4) olive oil composed of refined olive oils and VOOs, and 5) olive-pomace oil. Annex 1C.2 reports definitions and descriptions of these, as regulated by Reg. (EU) 1308/2013 (cons. 2020). One of the most relevant parameters for olive oil classification is free acidity content, expressed as concentrations of oleic acid. The greater the degree of hydrolysis and, therefore, of free fatty acids, the lower oil quality and the greater the risk of subsequent chemical alteration.

The catalogue of parameters of interest and influence for nutritional quality, safety, authenticity, and transparency, concerning the VOO supply chain, along with information about how these can be monitored, is reported in Annex 1D.

The main parameters of interest for nutritional quality are fatty acids (FA) composition, diacylglycerols (DAGs), total polyphenols content, secoiridoids content (oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol), and pigments, which are also relevant for several supply chain steps from cultivation and growth to oil extraction and separation. The chemical composition of the oil and olives is a complex interaction between the environment (e.g., climate, soil chemical and physical-chemical characteristics), agronomic factors (e.g., crop load, irrigation, harvest period and method), and the cultivar. These factors influence chemical compounds that affect colour (pigments), aroma (volatiles), and taste (phenols). Influence parameters on polyphenols and FA compositions in the cultivation and growth step are the climate (temperature in particular) and nitrogen status (Angerosa, Campestre and Giansante, 2006; Erel *et al.*, 2013).

During cultivation and growth, excessive irrigation prior to harvest can decrease oil content and quality, while too little irrigation decreases oil content, but may increase quality (Shahidi and Kiritsakis, 2017, p. 124). An example of a weather condition effect is frost damage that causes slight decreases in chlorophyll and carotenoid contents, and a significant decrease in concentrations of secoiridoid derivatives and 4-(acetoxymethyl)-1,2-dihydroxy-benzene (3,4-DHPEA-AC), which have a key role in oil stability and sensory attributes (Romero and Motilva, 2010).

The harvesting method has little direct effect on olive fruits or oil quality, unless causing damage to the fruit, or fruits are harvested overripe when they are more susceptible to damage. Mechanical harvesting can cause internal damage, inducing rapid softening and decay. Oils produced from mechanically harvested olives have similar FA compositions, but lower tocopherol (Vitamin E) and total phenolic contents, as well as lower oxidative stabilities than oils from manually harvested olives (Yousfi, Weiland and García, 2012).

During processing phases, malaxing is extremely important and many studies have been carried out to investigate its influence on quality. Altering conditions, such as time, temperature, and atmospheric composition, can influence the activities of enzymes in the olive paste, which are responsible for nutrient and bioactive profiles as well as organoleptic properties of the final product. Moreover, increasing malaxing time and temperature decreases concentrations of two subclasses of polyphenols in olive paste, namely secoiridoid aglycons and phenolic alcohols (Angerosa *et al.*, 2001). Phenolic bioactives have caught the attention of the scientific community because they have interesting biological properties (Gorzynik-Debicka *et al.*, 2018; González-Burgos and Gómez-Serranillos, 2021) and potential health benefits.

Secoiridoids, mainly oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol in olive oil, inhibit (a) blood platelet aggregation and synthesis of thromboxane, a potent vasoconstrictor and stimulus for platelet aggregation and (b) phospholipids and LDL oxidation; and (c) protect erythrocytes from oxidative damage (Morales and Lucas, 2010).

The presence of linoleic acids, and small amounts of linolenic acids, makes olive oil susceptible to oxidation. Most of the undesirable changes in taste and flavour in olive oil, caused by formation of non-volatile oxidation products, can be attributed to reactions caused by oxidative degradation of lipids, which are accelerated by light, temperature, enzymes, and metalloproteins (Morales and Przybylski, 2013). These reactions occur mostly during olive storage but also oil extraction and separation steps.

Chemical (e.g., polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, toxic and potentially toxic elements), biological (mycotoxins and moulds), and physical contaminants (e.g., radionuclides) are parameters of interest for food safety. Concentrations depend on many factors, such as the physical-chemical characteristics of soil, amounts of biocides and plant protection products used, and the presence of anthropogenic pollution sources. Chemical contaminants can arise during processing due to poor cleaning and disinfection and particular attention should be paid to the most toxic, such as mercury, lead, chromium, and cadmium, which can also bio-accumulate in the human body (Preedy and Watson, 2010).

The use of oil in meal preparation (e.g., catering or domestic) is a key step in preserving nutraceuticals. Polyphenols, pigments, and secoiridoids, as well as volatile compounds in general, can be destroyed by high

temperature. If oil is heated to its smoke point acrolein is formed, which is toxic to humans (Stevens and Maier, 2008).

Because of the lack of specific instructions for storage, mistreatment of the oil is common, even by consumers who use it traditionally. Shelf-life is influenced by several factors, including olive quality and processing technologies. Proper storage conditions and packaging are of great importance. Stainless steel tanks, tinplate metal vessels, and dark glass containers protect the oil from oxygen and light and, consequently, oxidation of phenolic compounds (Tsimidou, 2006).

After extensive research on the chemical characterisation of olive oils from different locations, sometimes even the same cultivar, there is now sufficient information to suggest chemical compositions of the oils is associated partially with provenance (Conte *et al.*, 2019). Geographical origin is particularly relevant since olive fruits are cultivated outside the Mediterranean area. However, even for the same olive type, locations create compositional differences amongst oils (Aparicio and Harwood, 2013). The most relevant parameters of interest to verify geographical origin are isotope ratio of light and heavier elements (H, C, O, Sr), rare earth elements, and some organic compounds, such as FAs, triglycerides, volatile organic compounds, and pigments. Minor components of olive oils, such as chlorophylls and carotenoids, are useful to some extent in investigating origins as well as for monitoring stability, storage history, and types of adulterations (Uncu and Ozen, 2020). EVOO is frequently adulterated with olive pomace, sunflower, rapeseed, hazelnut, corn, walnut, and soybean oils. Oleuropein-related molecules (recently found only in leaves) are markers of fraudulent addition of leaves during olive milling (Preedy and Watson, 2010, pp. 95–100).

3.2 Milk

Milk, intended as in Reg. (EU) 1308/2013 (cons. 2020) (“*product of the milking of one or more cows*”) is representative of terrestrial animal origin products. Dairy cattle are members of the genus *Bos taurus* and their milk is one of the most produced and consumed agricultural commodities worldwide; milk and dairy products account for about 14% of global agricultural trade (FAO, 2016). Currently, the European Union is the global lead in bovine milk production and the main exporter of skimmed milk powder (Hocquette and Gigli, 2005). Thus milk is one of the most important European commodities, particularly in central Europe countries although the main producers are Germany, France, the Netherlands, Poland, Italy, and Spain (CLAL, 2021). Milk has a key nutritional role, i.e., milk and dairy products supply energy and significant amounts of high-quality protein as well as micronutrients including calcium, magnesium, selenium, riboflavin, vitamins B5 and B12, which are essential in reducing hunger and malnutrition, particularly amongst the most vulnerable populations.

Inclusion of milk as a model in the search engine development allows research questions such as nutritional quality attributes, and development of breeding and husbandry to improve milk quality and safety, e.g., reduction in veterinary drug residues. Furthermore, having the tool developed for milk means it can be extended latterly to dairy products. Processes from forage feeding and farming practices to milk consumption are reported in Annex 2A, while definitions, and inputs and outputs for each step are reported in Annex 2B.

Milk can be classified by heat treatment—Ultra-High Temperature (UHT), microfiltered, pasteurised, sterilised—or by fat content—whole, semi-skimmed, or skimmed—as illustrated in Annexes 2C.1 and 2C.2.

Parameters of interest and influence for nutritional quality, safety, authenticity, and transparency for the milk supply chain, along with some information on how these can be monitored, is reported in Annex 2D.

Parameters of interest for nutritional quality included FA, provitamins (β -carotene, ergosterol), vitamins (A, B, D, E, C), phenolic compounds, and some minerals (especially selenium and iodine). Parameters of influence were forage/ feed compositions and quality (e.g., plant species eaten, organic or conventional forage), climatic and pedoclimatic conditions (season, weather, day length). All milk FAs are derived, almost equally, either directly from pre-formed FAs in the diet, or produced *de novo* in the mammary gland (Kalač, 2017, p. 37).

An example of the influence of grass-based diets on milk is the year-long study of 74 groups of 700 farms in four European countries (France, Norway, Slovakia, and Slovenia), varying widely both geographically (latitude and altitude) and the diets of lactating cows. Grass-based diets were found to be best method for producing milk with high n-3 FA contents, while corn-silage based diets, high in linoleic acid, resulted in milk with high n-6 FA contents (Griffiths, 2010; Chassaing *et al.*, 2016, p. 17). In another study, a higher content of phenolic compounds was observed when cows received a pasture-based diet compared with winter feeding (Lucas *et al.*, 2005).

Other parameters of interest are related to the cows, e.g., breed, stage of lactation, number of offspring. Lactational status is the most relevant influencer on milk composition. The contents of both total protein and casein are high in early lactation but, during late lactation (last month of milk production), several changes occur and impacted negatively the production of milk, i.e., increased pH, altered salts balance, increased activities of proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes, and reduced casein concentrations, as a proportion of total protein (Griffiths, 2010, p. 15, 16). Maillard reaction products are one of the main parameters of interest for nutritional quality, after heat treatment. Some occurred in milk after prolonged heating or inadequate storage. Indeed, furosine, one of the first products of the initial phase Maillard reaction, is used as milk quality indicator (Cho, Hong and Kim, 2012).

Many tests are used to verify whether milk meets hygienic and qualitative requirements stated in EU legislation (Reg. 2073/2005 (EC) cons. 2020) and evaluate efficiency of heat treatment. The most common

change is hydrolytic rancidity, which releases free FAs and modifies the organoleptic profile (causing a bitter taste and a sharp, unpleasant aroma). Lipoprotein lipase (LPL), an indigenous bacterial enzyme, causes rancidity by producing short chain FAs, particularly butyric acid. LPL is active at the fat/water interface but is ineffective unless the fat globule membrane is damaged or weakened. This may occur through agitation, and/or foaming, and pumping. For this reason, homogenized milk is subject to rapid lipolysis unless lipases are first destroyed by heating (Deeth, 2021).

From a safety point of view, milk is a perishable product, because it is a nutritious substrate for microorganisms. Microbial contamination occurs mainly during and after milking. Microorganisms in bulk tank milk originate from the interior of teats (*Staphylococcus aureus*), the farm environment, and from surfaces of the milking equipment (e.g., *Bacillus cereus* spores, *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*). Although most of them are inactivated by thermal processing technologies, they can be found in processed products depending on the type of heat treatment used (Tamime, 2009). Spoilage microflora in pasteurised milk arise either as (a) post-pasteurization microbial contaminants, which enter the milk after heating, and/or (b) heat-resistant bacteria. To reduce or eliminate microbial contamination from the farm to the dairy plant, it is essential that utensils and equipment are properly cleaned.

Other relevant parameters of interest for food safety are veterinary drugs and phthalates residues. Antibiotics use may result in residues in the milk when the milk is collected during the prescribed withdrawal period (i.e., period after a drug is administered to when the concentration falls below tolerance). Both the dairy industry and EU food safety authorities monitor antibiotics, as indicated by Directive 96/23/EC. Somatic cell counting is used routinely to detect intramammary infection that cause mastitis. Disinfectants have found as residues in milk. For example, iodine is found as quaternary ammonium compound (QAC) residues and chloroform residues (van Asselt *et al.*, 2017). Phthalates are found in milk and dairy products, presumably from PVC tubing used during milking or transfer from bulk to storage tanks, as well as packaging plastic materials. Phthalates are classified as endocrine disruptors and have been linked to adverse health effects, particularly in infants; time and temperature are the main parameters of influence to monitor in the supply steps. If temperature abuse occurs, this will result in a range of metabolites and enzymes. At the same time, if heat treatments are not well-monitored, the Maillard reaction may contribute to neof ormation of contaminants, such as lactulosyl-lysine or fructosyl-lysine, pyrrolidine, and carboxymethyllysine, founded previously in infant formula products within Europe (Birlouez-Aragon *et al.*, 2010).

It can be useful to examine milk to determine cows' diets, geographical origin, and zoologic origin (specific breed). Terpenes, especially sesquiterpenes, make it possible to discriminate between geographical origins of milks, based on botanical type of forage (Fernandez *et al.*, 2003). β -carotene measurements allow distinctions between milk from maize silage and milks from grass silage or pasture (Ferlay *et al.*, 2002). Stable isotope ratio analysis (H, C, N, O, S) provided evidence relating to both dietary background and geographical origin (O'Sullivan, Schmidt and Monahan, 2022). Furthermore, the FA composition, namely the long chain unsaturated fatty acids, can be useful in differentiating milk from cows grazing on lowland or highland pastures (Bugaud *et al.*, 2001).

Adulteration in milk is commonplace. Some adulterants can have serious adverse health effects, e.g., commercial urea, which is used to increase non-protein nitrogen content; alkalis, which are used to correct/optimize pH; hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), which prolongs shelf life; sugar, which increases carbohydrate content and density; and melamine, which is used to increase apparent protein content reported in analytical testing. Melamine was used in one of the largest deliberate food contamination incidents in 2008: 300,000 Chinese infants and young children were affected and six deaths were reported (Gossner *et al.*, 2009). Other common adulterations, which do not pose serious risks for human health, are processing milk obtained from different species, addition of vegetable protein (e.g., soy), and addition of whey and water (Azad and Ahmed, 2016). Lactulose and furosine can be used as markers of improper addition of reconstituted milk powder to liquid milk as well as heat damage indicators (Cho, Hong and Kim, 2012).

3.3 Fishery products

Fishery products include all seawater or freshwater animals intended as in the Regulation (EC) 853/2004 (cons. 2021). Currently, fish and seafood are some of the most traded food items in the world, representing one of the main commodities of Nordic countries, where about 70% of the total EU catch was taken (European Commission, 2020a). The rapid rate of expansion of worldwide trade in fish and fish products in recent decades is due to globalisation, but many issues are still affecting fish and seafood supply chains, such as lack of transparency, illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing trade, fraud and species substitution, integrity, and seafood safety (Blaha and Katafono, 2020).

As described in the general design section (7.1), three different supply chains were examined, as examples of food product categories covering various types of fishery products (Rehbein and Oehlschläger, 2009; CREA, 2019a):

- 1) Atlantic salmon (*Salmon salar*) - representative of the aquaculture line, large size, and high fat fish
- 2) Common sole (*Solea solea*) - representative of a marine wild-caught, medium size, and very low-fat fish
- 3) European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) - representative of a marine wild-caught, small size, low fat fish

The supply chain of fishery products in general, starting from water and ending with consumption included both aquaculture and marine wild-caught fish. All the possible commercial routes are outlined in Annex 3A. Atlantic salmon aquaculture, common sole, and European anchovy supply chains are described in Annexes 3.1A, 3.2A, 3.3A, respectively. Specific definitions, along with inputs and outputs, are explained generally for fishery products in Annex 3B, and specifically for Atlantic salmon (Annex 3.1B), common sole (Annex 3.2B), and anchovy (Annex 3.3B). In these Annexes, green rows highlight steps that can heavily impact sustainability and include processing by-products as secondary raw materials (e.g., flour, oil, paste). A module with definitions for fishery terms is reported in Annex 3C. Parameters of interest and influence for nutritional quality, safety, authenticity, and transparency, and information about how they can be monitored, are reported in Annex 3.1C for salmon, Annex 3.2C for common sole, and Annex 3.3C for anchovies.

It should also be mentioned that fish products can have long supply chains but also short supply chains (from farm direct to the consumer).

3.3.1 Common aspects

Fish is the world's last major source of wild protein, providing at least 20% of intake for a third of the world's population. Proteins in fish make up 15-20% of total chemical composition (Mohanty *et al.*, 2019); this is higher in lean fish. FAs composition varies widely amongst fish and depends on factors such as species, diet, and environment like salinity, temperature, season, geographical location, and whether fish are wild or farmed (Balami, Sharma and Karn, 2019).

There are some common parameters of interest in all fish supply chains, such as organoleptic profile (e.g., texture), peroxide value, K-value, thiobarbituric acid (TBA) and total volatile base (TVB) values. Trimethylamine anhydrous (TMA) is the most prevalent volatile nitrogen compound formed in seawater fish. Flesh quality is determined by a combination of characteristics including extrinsic factors, such as freshness, pre- and post-slaughter handling procedures, and intrinsic traits, such as morphometric characteristics, flesh chemical composition and sensory profile attributes. These parameters are affected by others including season, fish size, maturation, and water quality (Parma *et al.*, 2019).

Fresh fish are highly perishable due to their chemical composition. Enzymatic activity reduces organoleptic quality relatively quickly, and microorganisms on the skin, gills, and gut multiply and invade tissues soon after harvest. Specific analyses are used to evaluate fish freshness. Some of these measure changes in fat and proteins, e.g., fat (TBA and peroxide value) and nitrogen-rich compounds, such as proteins (TVB, TMA). Autolytic and bacterial conversion of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) into hypoxanthine occurs typically after death. This reaction is evaluated by K-values, which measures formation of ammonia, causing deteriorations in quality. In addition, modification of lipids (deterioration of polyunsaturated fatty acids) during processing and storage is one of the main causes of off-flavours. Time, temperature, humidity, and efficiency of handling practices are, therefore, the main parameters of influence.

Safety of fish largely depends on management methods along the production chain from conservation to transformation, and distribution. Under normal refrigerated storage conditions, shelf-life is limited by enzymatic and microbiological spoilage. Pathogens such as *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Clostridium botulinum* type E, *Vibrio spp.*, *Aeromonas spp.*, and faecal bacteria and viruses contaminate fish, leading to foodborne illness. The parasites *Anisakis* does not represent a danger for farmed salmon because it does not consume potentially infected hosts (Wootten, Yoon and Bron, 2010).

During processing, fish products can be contaminated by biological, chemical, and physical contaminants. The majority of seafood-borne outbreaks are associated with biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine) (EFSA, 2015). The most important biogenic amine in fish is histamine and it is most frequently implicated in outbreaks associated with fish and fishery products. Histamine causes food poisoning similar to an allergic reaction. Although scombroid fishes are primarily implicated, non-scombroid species including salmon and anchovies have also been involved (Nuñez, del Olmo and Calzada, 2016).

Many efforts have been made through legislation (e.g. 178/2002 Common Food Law), international treaties, and voluntary agreements to reduce illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing, but a lack of universally implemented dissuasive sanctioning schemes continues to allow loopholes that IUU fishing operators can exploit (OECD, 2017).

Common parameters of interest for authenticity identified in the fishery products supply chains were stable isotopic ratios as well as morphological, lipidic, genomic, and proteomic profiles. Stable isotopes ratios reflect both the environment in which fish are grown and composition of their diet. There are several correlations between isotope ratios and geo/climatic environment. ^{13}C and ^{15}N are related to diet, while ^{18}O and ^2H are influenced by origins of water in the final product (EFSA, 2015). Stable isotope ratios for carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen have also been suggested as a means for discriminating between wild and farmed fish, and between organic and intensively farm fish, based on differences in feed origin. Another approach for tracing the origin of seafood, and methods of production, is analysis of FAs. The effects of different types of lipids in the diet on growth and tissue FA composition have been investigated for several cultured and wild species. In all cases, farmed fish were found to have a much higher lipid contents than wild counterparts, and the FA profiles of farmed fish reflected the FA composition of their diet (Moretti *et al.*, 2003).

3.3.2 Peculiarities for Atlantic salmon

Figure 2. Atlantic salmon (SeaFoodSource, 2014b)

Atlantic salmon is a species of ray-finned fish in the family *Salmonidae* with a maximum length of 76 cm (NOAA Fisheries, no date). The supply chain of Atlantic salmon is more complex than other fishery products, due to farming and multitude of final products (e.g., smoked, canned, etc).

Salmon is a fatty fish, because fats are estimated to be ca. 12 g/ 100 g (CREA, 2019c). It is a source of omega-3 fatty acids (1.9 g per 100 g) and vitamins (B3 [niacin], A, B2, D). Omega-3 fatty acid and vitamin contents, and fish stress indicators, are the main parameters of interest for nutritional quality (Taşbozan and Gökçe, 2017). In traditional salmon farming, fish are produced in land-based systems with fresh or low salinity brackish water from hatching to smolting. After smolting, fish are moved to net pens in the sea where they grow to market size. Measuring stress indicators in fish is necessary to determine how health and welfare are being influenced by interactions with humans during farming (from juvenile salmon production to salmon crowding). Parameters of influence that can affect fish stress including lighting, oxygen, density, and temperature. Stress in captive populations (e.g., hatcheries, farms) is often assessed to reduce with a view to reducing it and, therefore, maximize growth and survival. Examples of stress indicators and oxidative stress are plasma cortisol, reactive oxygen species (ROS), immediate early genes and transcription factors, intracellular enzymes, steroid hormones, and metabolites such as glucose and lactate, and leukocytes (Sopinka *et al.*, 2016).

During farming, feed composition influences nutrient composition of salmon flesh, mostly in terms of polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), such as omega-3, vitamins (B6, D, B12), and minerals (iodine, selenium, calcium, iron, sodium, and phosphorus).

In aquaculture, viral infections are readily transmitted because of high density and associated with chronic stress (Kibenge, 2016). Viruses that affect aquaculture fish stock include *Piscine orthoreovirus* (PRV) (Kibenge, 2019) and *Salmon isavirus*. Bacteria can also affect aquaculture of Atlantic salmon and other fish, leading to Piscirickettsiosis, a disease caused by the intracellular Gram-negative bacterium *Piscirickettsia salmonis*. This bacterium caused significant economic losses in Chile during 2020-2021 (approximately US \$500 million; Mukiibi *et al.*, 2021). Genomic and proteomic profiles may also be analysed to demonstrate authenticity and transparency, along with isotopic analysis, which allows differentiation of farmed from wild salmon, and organic from conventionally farmed salmon. Scottish farmed salmon has a protected geographical indication, as approved by Reg. 1195/2008 (EC).

3.3.3 Peculiarities for the common sole

Figure 3. Common sole (SeaFoodSource, 2014c)

The common European sole is a species of flatfish in the family *Soleidae* and is known as Dover sole with the binomial name of *Solea solea* (Linnaeus, 1758) or *Solea vulgaris* (Quensel, 1806). It is highly valued by consumers for its taste. Its maximum length is around 58 cm. Although there has been an expansion in sole aquaculture production, we considered only wild-caught of sole.

Sole is a lean species with 1.4 g fat per 100 g of fats and has a high protein content (ca. 17 g per 100 g). The content of PUFAs n-3 in raw sole is 34.4% of total FAs, which is lower than fattier species such as salmon. Another parameter of interest for nutritional quality was vitamin content, particularly niacin (B3, 14 mg per 100 g) and retinol (vitamin A, 32 µg per 100 g) (CREA, 2019d). Factors affecting FAs composition in wild fish can be endogenous (e.g., life cycle stage) or exogenous including environmental changes, fluctuations in availability and compositions of feed, and season. FAs compositions of common sole is substantially different between seasons (Gökçe *et al.*, 2004). Also, in wild sole, eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and dehydroascorbic acid (DHA) contents are less than half that found in farmed sole (Parma *et al.*, 2019).

From a safety point of view, soles undergo a metamorphosis with drastic morphological and physiological changes, which makes them potentially more vulnerable to pollutants than other fish. The benthic lifestyle exposes flatfishes to a wide range of contaminants, including - but not limited to - endocrine disruptors, toxic and potentially toxic elements, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), and dioxins (Sardi *et al.*, 2021).

3.3.4 Peculiarities for European anchovy

Figure 4. European anchovy (SeaFoodSource, 2014a)

European anchovy (*Engraulis encrasicolus*) is a marine bony fish belonging to the family *Engraulidae*. Anchovies are tiny silvery fish with blue-green backs. Their maximum length is around 20 cm. They are caught by deep-water trawlers, and most are canned, salted, turned into paste or distilled. Fat content is low (2.6 g per 100 g) but they have a high protein content (16.8 g per 100 g) (CREA, 2019b). Oleic acid, EPA, and DHA are the most prevalent monounsaturated fatty acids (6.7% of total FAs per edible 100 g, 9.6% of

monounsaturated fats and 18.5% of monounsaturated fats, respectively). Anchovy oil is a major source of commercial EPA and DHA. The omega 6:omega 3 ratio is 1: 5 (Assoittica Italia, 2022).

Microplastics have been found in the European anchovy, and these can translocate to contaminate different organs (Collard *et al.*, 2017).

3.4 Monitoring of parameters of interest and parameters of influence

Besides presenting parameters of interest and influence, Annex 1D, 2D, 3.1C, 3.2C, and 3.3C also report a summary of systems and approaches used to monitor them. They include analytical techniques (off-line procedures including sampling, sample pre-treatment and instrumental analysis) and *in situ* and on-line monitoring using sensors and portable devices.

Analytical techniques for chemical analyses must be selected according to the analyte, and are usually based on chromatography, atomic or molecular spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, or nuclear magnetic resonance. Hyphenated techniques are also often used:

- Chromatography can be used to determine:
 - 1) Nutritional quality
 - vitamins, through high-performance liquid chromatography with UV detector (HPLC-UV) or coupled with mass spectrometry (LC-MS) (Zhang *et al.*, 2018)
 - polyphenols, by liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) (López-Fernández *et al.*, 2020)
 - fatty acids, by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) (Bratu *et al.*, 2013) and gas chromatography equipped with hydrogen flame ionization detector (GC/FID) (Muhammad Alinafiah *et al.*, 2021)
 - 2) Food safety
 - mycotoxins, by gas or liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC-MS, HPLC-MS, HPLC-MS/MS, and UFLC–MS/MS), or thin-layer chromatography (TLC) (Amelin, Karaseva and Tret'yakov, 2013)
 - Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) by HPLC with fluorescence detector (HPLC-FLD) and GC-MS (Ishizaki *et al.*, 2010; Mastovska *et al.*, 2015)
 - antibiotic residues by HPLC, ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC), ion pair chromatography (IPC), or reversed-phase liquid chromatographic (RPLC) (Wang, MacNeil and Kay, 2011)
 - 3) Food authenticity
 - lipid profile by GC-MS (Pastor, Ačanski and Vujić, 2019)
- Molecular spectroscopy techniques, such as UV-Vis and near infra-red spectroscopy (NIR), can be used to determine fibres, fats, water content, carotenoids, sugars, and many other compositional parameters as well as food safety and food authenticity (e.g. geographical traceability) (Oliveira and Franca, 2011; Qu *et al.*, 2015).
- Atomic spectroscopy techniques, such as atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES), can be used to determine mineral content of foods

(Mohanty *et al.*, 2016), for nutritional quality as well as monitoring of toxic and potentially toxic elements in trace and ultra-trace amounts.

- Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) can be applied to determine amino acids, lipids, and sugars in relation to nutritional quality. Solid-state high-resolution NMR methods have been applied to many foods to characterize different molecular fractions (carbohydrates, proteins, and lipids) in solid food matrices (Sacchi and Paolillo, 2007). Proton nuclear magnetic resonance (1H-NMR) can be used for determination of contaminants potentially released by food contact materials (e.g., polyolefin) for food safety.
- Mass spectrometry can be used for several purposes, often hyphenated with other techniques (as reported for examples above). Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) can be used to determine nutrients (nutritional quality) or toxic and potentially toxic elements at ultra-trace concentrations, even when they are released from food contact materials and food contact surfaces (food safety) (Bosnak and Pruszkowski, 2011; Hajeb *et al.*, 2014), or for defining rare earth element profiles for determination of origins (authenticity). Furthermore, isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS) is the primary technique for stable isotope ratio analysis of light elements (for food authenticity control, e.g., geographical origin) (Kelly, 2003). For example, strontium isotopic composition analysis using multi-collector ICP-MS has been shown to be suitable for authentication of olive oil (Royer *et al.*, 1999; Lukić *et al.*, 2019). Isotopes may allow milk and dairy products from different regions to be distinguished or different feeding regimens to be distinguished from one another other, except in cases where feed, farming environment, and agriculture practices are similar (Tamime, 2009; Wijenayake *et al.*, 2020). Life cycles of fishery products are usually more complicated than other agriproducts, and stable isotope ratios analysis has been suggested only for a small number of applications (Naaum and Hanner, 2016). Some studies have shown that stable isotope contents reflect both the environment and the composition of diet. Isotopes of strontium could be indicative of geographic origin, since this element is present together with calcium in bones or calcified materials of seafood (Eurofins Analytics France, Morin and Lees, 2018)
- Microbiological analyses – with classical or modified culture methods – can be used for detection of foodborne microorganisms. Molecular methods, such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), enzyme-linked fluorescent assay (ELFA), and conventional, real-time, and multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) are widely applied as well as direct epifluorescent filter technique using microscopy, flow cytometry, and the adenosine triphosphate (ATP) bioluminescence assay (Húngaro *et al.*, 2014). An example is the rapid automated bacterial impedance technique (RABIT) for the rapid detection of bacteria, yeasts, and moulds. The Bax System, which consists of automated real-time PCR, can be applied for detection of *Salmonella*, *E. coli* O 157:H7, *L. monocytogenes*, *Listeria* spp., and some moulds and yeasts
- DNA-based analyses can be used for food quality, authenticity, and food safety. They use different markers, amplified fragments, or restriction profiling (e.g., simple sequence repeats, single nucleotide polymorphisms, amplified fragments length polymorphism). DNA analyses can reveal cultivars used for oil production through the presence of unique DNA sequences from different plant species (e.g., hazelnut, sunflower, rapeseed, corn, or soy) and different cultivars (e.g., the presence of non-PDO cultivars in a product claiming to be PDO monovarietal) (Vietina, Agrimonti and Marmioli, 2013; Batrinou *et al.*, 2020). By customizing PCR-based techniques for milk fat analysis, simple and reliable DNA-based protocols can be designed to assess authenticity or identify plant oils adulteration (Uncu and Uncu, 2020). For fishery products, DNA analyses are used for species identification. At the point of landing, for example, DNA analyses are used mainly to detect illegal, unreported, and unregulated fishing. If the local populations of fish have distinctive features, DNA marker analyses can be used to verify geographical origins (Naaum and Hanner, 2016). In food safety, fluorescent *in situ* hybridization (FISH) uses fluorescent probes to detect small deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) or ribonucleic acid (RNA) sequences, or – at a larger scale – microarrays (DNA microchip). In general, the application of omics-based approaches

(metagenomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and metabolomics) is increasing for studying food-associated microorganisms in support of both food quality and safety (Cook and Nightingale, 2018).

Several parameters related to nutritional quality, safety, and authenticity verification can be monitored *in situ* and on-line using sensors and portable devices. They can be applied to monitor parameters of influence such as environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, air humidity, rainfall, lightening, wind speed) and characteristics of growing soils and irrigation waters (e.g., pH, electric potential) as well as process and storage conditions (e.g., temperature, time). Sensor-based systems can also be used for off-line laboratory measurements, such as the electronic nose.

Data and information collected during primary production and processing can be reported in a logbook for track and trace purposes. Food businesses must identify and document information on products “one step forward and one step back” in the food chain (Reg. 178/2002, Reg. 1169/2011). Reg. (EC) 1224/2009 (cons. 2019) specifies requirements for fishing logbooks, where information such as FAO codes for the catches, types of gear used, dates, etc., must be reported.

The logbook is also mentioned by the Italian Presidential Decree 55/2012 based on Reg. (EC) 178/2002 (cons. 2021) as a “register of the processing operations” that indicates the phytosanitary treatments during the cultivation phase.

4 Search engine concept

The purpose of the traceability search engine concept is to support users in searching and finding available food data and information and provides background knowledge to its users. More specifically, the traceability search engine concept uses tags with semantic meaning, groups them in dimensions, assigns tags to each data point or information resource, and thereby allows visual space searches, and offers background information about the food supply chain and the different process steps. Below, terms are defined and dimensions explained, as well as searching and presentation of information.

The screenshot shows the FNS-Cloud search engine interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Catalogues', 'News', 'myFNS-Cloud', 'Contact', and 'LOGIN'. Below the navigation bar, there are two tabs: 'Table Search' (selected) and 'Standard Search'. The search interface includes two dimensions for filtering:

- * Dimension 1 - vertically:** A dropdown menu with 'Food area' selected.
- * Dimension 2 - horizontally:** A dropdown menu with 'Target audience' selected.

Below the dimensions, there are two more dropdown menus:

- * foodTopicAreas:** A dropdown menu with '15 selected'.
- * targetAudiences:** A dropdown menu with '4 selected'.

At the bottom of the search interface, there are two buttons: 'SEARCH' and 'CLEAR'.

Below the search interface, there is a section titled 'SEARCH RESULTS'. The results are displayed in a grid format with columns for different target audiences: 'Business & Developers', 'General Public', 'Government Agencies', and 'Researchers & Scientists'. The results are grouped by food area: 'Agri-Food', 'Food & Drug Interaction', and 'Nutrition & Health'. Each group shows a list of search results with their respective target audiences.

Figure 5. Browsing datasets in the search engine – 2 dimensions are chosen, with 33 and 4 tags for each.

The first term that the search engine concept uses is data or information resource, which can be a dataset or a scientific publication. Such data or information resources can have any form or format; they can be structured, semi-structured or unstructured data or information. While structured data or information, such as databases or Excel files, have data organised in a specific order, such as rows and columns, unstructured data, or information (such as free text) does not use an ordered structure and data and information must be extracted. Semi-structured data and information is somewhere in-between structured and unstructured, and normally combines them. An example might be a Wiki, where each term is explained on a separate page

(list), but the content of a page is free text and, therefore, unstructured. This structural classification is a high-level classification, while more concrete types of data or information resources are commonly used, such as datasets, databases, Wikis, scientific papers, project reports or websites. The concept does not require that data and information resources are uploaded into the software. The software only requires that a resource is described with enough details that can be used for search.

Type of a resource is the first characterisation of data or an information resource, and a dimension in the concept. A dimension has different tags, where a tag is a term or keyword that can be assigned to a resource describing an aspect of the resource (see Figure 38). The dimension is, therefore, a group of data or information resources while the tags are concrete values, such as dataset, scientific publication, or Wiki.

Figure 6. A dimension is a group of tags which are possible concrete terms or keywords of the dimension.

For each resource, none, one, or multiple tags in or across dimensions can be assigned. Tags and dimensions have a name and a description explaining their meaning and usage. Additional fields can be added, such as inputs and outputs.

Tags within a dimension can also have a hierarchical structure, creating a tree structure hierarchy with multiple parent terms. In the food traceability search engine concept, the following dimensions are defined:

- a. Type - defines the type of the resource
- b. Food group/matrix - describes a group of foods or a single food item
- c. Food supply chain - describes for each food group/matrix a separate chain of phases
- d. Country - defines the country of origin for the data or information of a resource
- e. Main aspects of food science used in this concept—tags are nutritional quality, safety, and authenticity/traceability (based on the outcome of the former section)
- f. Research area - defines a comprehensive list of research aspects in food science which can change over time
- g. Target audience - defines different user groups such as primary producers, processors, distributors, retailers, consumers, researchers, inspection and control agencies, certification bodies, authorities, and policymakers
- h. Access mode - defines how a resource can be accessed, e.g., open access, restricted access, or no access
- i. Year - defines the year of a resource
- j. Chemical substance - defines the list of nutrients, contaminants, and other chemical substances
- k. Parameter of interest - describes properties of foods that are of interest to traceability in combination with nutritional quality, safety, and authenticity/transparency. Parameters of influence are facts that have an influence on the measurement of the parameter of interest

[Home](#) > [Catalogues](#) > [Datasets](#)

BROWSE DATASETS

This tool, which is an integral part of FNS-Cloud, allows to browse the collected Datasets based on the searched phrase, or by selected available Food Areas (from among the Agri-Food, Biological Activity, Food & Drug interaction, Food Intake & Lifestyle or Nutrition and Health domain). Each dataset provides general information about the dataset (description, contact data, technical details, collaboration possibilities, and other info).

[Table Search](#) [Standard Search](#)

* Dimension 1 - vertically:

Food area ▼

- Food supply chain
- Main aspects
- Food area
- Target audience
- Access mode
- Parameter of interest

* foodTopicAreas:

15 selected ▼

* targetAudiences:

4 selected ▼

Figure 7. Choosing first dimension

The food supply chain is another example of a dimension and each step in the chain is a tag.

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BROWSE DATASETS

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[Table Search](#) [Standard Search](#)

* Dimension 1 - vertically:

Target audience ▼

* Dimension 2 - horizontally:

Dimension 2 ▼

SEARCH

CLEAR

* targetAudiences:

Target Audiences ▼

- Business & Developers
- General Public
- Government Agencies
- Researchers & Scientists
- Service Providers

Figure 8. Choosing first tag

Two or more dimensions can have inter-dependencies. For example, the dimensions food group or matrix and the dimension food supply chain. Depending on the food group, the food supply chain can be different.

The concept, therefore, allows dependency rules for tags and dimensions to be defined. A dependency rule for dimensions allows definition of each food group's food supply chain.

Another example is parameter of interest, which is a super dimension, where all other dimensions are child dimensions; these are separated because they represent a specific aspect of the parent dimension.

A dependency rule between tags allows defines how tags in one dimension can occur in combination with tags from other dimensions, e.g., parameters of interest only occur in combinations with a certain phase in the supply chain (see Annexes 1D, 2D, 3.1C, 3.2C, 3.3C).

Descriptions of the dimensions and dependency rules are designed to inform users and serve as a knowledge and documentation basis in the search engine. Documentation should not only allow simple descriptions, but also advanced documentation, as shown in Annexes 1C.1, 1C.2, 2C.1, 2C.2, 3C. Documentation contains all the information collected for a food and represents current knowledge. As this develops over time, documentation will need to be updated.

Having assigned tags to the resources, these can be used to browse and search data and information resources. A simple search allows, therefore, selection of one or more tags from one or more dimensions to retrieve resources that have these tags. The result is presented as a list of resources. If more than one tag is used, “AND”, “OR” or “both” must be defined. The AND operator defines that resources must have all tags while OR defines that either may be assigned. Both will retrieve any resource with those tags, regardless of whether it is jointly or severally.

Figure 9. Search engine allows multiple tags as well as suggesting them

More interesting is the space search because presenting results in list form has some limitations. For instance, the list does not show where no resources are available and it also does not show how single results relate to each other, e.g., do they belong to the same supply chain step or to the same topic. A resulting list must be considered a keyhole where only a part of the whole is visible. The space search resolves this issue by allowing use of dimensions to span a result space. For example, if two dimensions are selected, tags of one dimension are put on one axis and the tags of the other on the other. This results in a table where data and information resources are listed in corresponding cells. Table 1 shows a schematic example where the food supply chain was used in combination with three aspects of food science, namely safety, quality, and authenticity and transparency.

	Primary production	Processing	Packaging	Storage and distribution	Retail	Final consumption
Safety						TDS data (link) Medication concentration data (link)
Nutritional quality		Possible contamination during olive oil extraction (link)		Loss of vitamins during storage (link)	Label information (link)	Greece food composition database (link)
Authenticity / transparency	Isotope data (link)					

Table 1. Example of result presentation of a 2-dimensional space search.

The resulting table shows how the keyhole is opened up to show all possible combinations of two dimensions by providing an overview of data and information resources that are available and where no resources are available. The example also shows that not all tags need to be mapped on an axis to reduce the number of columns and rows.

Considering different users and their needs, graphic presentations of the supply chains are beneficial, showing individual steps and the entire process from primary production to human intake. With this, users can see the complexity of a system as well as obtain detailed information about the phase that interests them.

The resulting cells are clickable and, when selected, another view with resources is presented, showing more information than in the multi-dimensional result space. The idea is that the list, or the result space, represent a short summary, while more information can be found on a separate page by clicking on an item. The list or search space result is called result view while the detail information page is called the detail view. How the detail view is structured and what information it contains depends on the data domain.

SEARCH RESULTS

	Business & Developers	General Public	Government Agencies	Researchers & Scientists
Agri-Food	Food data research	Search engine Food data research	Food data research FoodCASE Web app, mobile app and desktop app development	FoodCASE ONS FairSpace Web app, mobile app and desktop app development Food data research Search engine
				FairSpace
Food & Drug Interaction				FairSpace
Nutrition & Health	Food and nutrition research consultancy		Food and nutrition research consultancy	MATAFILER R/Rstudio/Bioconductor FairSpace
	Diet Assess and Plan - DAP	Diet Assess and Plan - DAP	Diet Assess and Plan - DAP	Quisper Food and nutrition research consultancy
	Quisper			Diet Assess and Plan - DAP PathVisio

Figure 10. Result of a search - datasets.

The space search is not limited to two dimensions, but it can combine three or more dimensions. Presentation of results is a challenge, as multi-dimensional spaces are hard to present and decomposition in multiple two-dimensional tables is needed. The concept also allows for combination of two or more dimensions on a single axis to increase the space and enlarge the overview of available resources. A limiting factor is space on the computer screen if mobile devices are used. In such cases, the reduction of tags mapped on axes is advisable.

5 How to Use the App

The app for the test environment can be found under <https://catalogues.test.fns.foodcase-services.com/catalogues/datasets>. This test environment contains several dummy datasets entered by users and programmers.

A user can choose "Standard search" (No. 1 in the picture below), which is used to find the result after entering a name or selecting the available criteria, or the new "Table Search"(No. 2 in the picture), which allows user to display the results in a table.

BROWSE DATASETS

This tool, which is an integral part of FNS-Cloud, allows to browse the collected Datasets based on the searched phrase, or by selected available Food Areas (from among the Agri-Food, Biological Activity, Food & Drug interaction, Food Intake & Lifestyle or Nutrition and Health domain). Each dataset provides general information about the dataset (description, contact data, technical details, collaboration possibilities, and other info).

Standard Search Table Search
1 **2**

After selecting Table Search, the user must decide first which axes (dimensions) and then which tags should appear in the search result. In the first field, the user selects dimension 1 (vertical axis) (No. 3). The following dimensions are available while more details about the dimensions can be found in section 4:

- Food Supply Chain
- Main Aspects
- Food area
- Target audience
- Access mode
- Parameter of interest

[Home](#) > [Catalogues](#) > [Datasets](#)

BROWSE DATASETS

This tool, which is an integral part of FNS-Cloud, allows to browse the collected Datasets based on the searched phrase, or by selected available Food Areas (from among the Agri-Food, Biological Activity, Food & Drug interaction, Food Intake & Lifestyle or Nutrition and Health domain). Each dataset provides general information about the dataset (description, contact data, technical details, collaboration possibilities, and other info).

Table Search Standard Search

* Dimension 1 - vertically: **3**

Dimension 1 ▼

- Food supply chain
- Main aspects
- Food area
- Target audience
- Access mode
- Parameter of interest

After selecting the vertical axis, the user can select the tags that will be displayed on the horizontal axis (No.4). As described in the section before, tags are concrete values of a dimension, and these steps allows a

simplification on the vertical axis of the resulting table. For example, a user does not want to show all possible entries along the food supply chain but is only interested in the first three steps. The user can therefore select the first three entries in this step and only the first three steps will be displayed in the resulting table.

[Home](#) > [Catalogues](#) > [Datasets](#)

BROWSE DATASETS

This tool, which is an integral part of FNS-Cloud, allows to browse the collected Datasets based on the searched phrase, or by selected available Food Areas (from among the Agri-Food, Biological Activity, Food & Drug interaction, Food Intake & Lifestyle or Nutrition and Health domain). Each dataset provides general information about the dataset (description, contact data, technical details, collaboration possibilities, and other info).

[Table Search](#) Standard Search

* Dimension 1 - vertically:
 ▼

* Dimension 2 - horizontally:
 ▼

* foodTopicAreas:

Food Topic Areas ▼

- Biological Activity
- ▶ Population group
- ▶ Tool used in collection
- ▶ Study name
- ▶ Food Intake & Lifestyle
- ▶ Data collection method
- ▶ Agri-Food
- ▶ Nutrition & Health
- ▶ Food & Drug Interaction
- ▶ Training and Education

Depending on the selected dimension, tags can be selected via:

- a list (e.g., Main aspects)

A list with the possibility of selecting specific options by clicking on the selected options. A green tick will appear next to the selected options to confirm the selected option.

2 selected ▼

- Business & Developers
- General Public ✓
- Government Agencies ✓
- Researchers & Scientists
- Service Providers

- a nested list (e.g., Food area)

This is a special kind of list that has options and nested options. The black triangle on the left informs that there are additional options here. To see them, select the triangle. A green square with tick will appear next to the selected options to confirm the selected option.

- a list with categories (Food supply chain)

After selecting the food supply chain, the user firstly must select a food group from the list, and secondly select the food supply chain steps (tags). The behaviour of the fields is the same as in lists.

Additionally, options from lists and nested lists are searchable. To use this functionality, a field can be clicked, and the user can start typing. The list of available results will reduce according to the user input.

After selecting Dimension 1 (vertical axis) options, the user must do the same for Dimension 2 (horizontal axis).

Table Search Standard Search

* Dimension 1 - vertically: * foodTopicAreas:

* Dimension 2 - horizontally:

Once, the user has selected dimension 1 and 2 and its tags, the search button can be pressed. At this point, the search is performed and after a while the answers will be available in the form of a table as shown in the following figure:

Table Search Standard Search

* Dimension 1 - vertically: * foodTopicAreas:

* Dimension 2 - horizontally: * targetAudiences:

SEARCH RESULTS

	Business & Developers	General Public	Government Agencies	Service Providers
Safety		Food shopping advisor Search engine	FoodCASE Web app, mobile app and desktop app development	
Toxicology		Food shopping advisor		
Agri-Food	Food data research	Food data research Search engine	FoodCASE Web app, mobile app and desktop app development Food data research	Food data research

The data in the two-dimensional table is read by looking at the first row at the top and the first column on the left. A cell lists all datasets that have the corresponding tags of the dimensions. If there is more than one dataset in a given cell, they are separated by a line. After clicking on a given dataset, user will be redirected to a page with the details about the dataset.

SEARCH RESULTS

	Business & Developers	General Public	Government Agencies	Service Providers
Safety		Food shopping advisor Search engine	FoodCASE Web app, mobile app and desktop app development	
Toxicology		Food shopping advisor		
Agri-Food	Food data research	Food data research Search engine	FoodCASE Web app, mobile app and desktop app development Food data research	Food data research

6 Conclusion

The traceability search engine concept followed the FAIR approach in collecting, organising, accessing, and integrating data and metadata describing food quality, safety, traceability, transparency, and authenticity of products along a given food supply chain. The concept developed is helpful for visualisation of the food supply chain and demonstrating the different types of searches. Searches can be made on dimensions alone or in combinations (type of resource, food/matrix group, food chain, country, aspects related to food science, research area, target audience, access mode, year, chemistry, the parameter of interest), or with their different tags (e.g., a step in a specific food supply chain). This concept allows user communities to find available food data and information and provides them with background knowledge. Indeed, depending on the expertise of users, more detailed information can be made available or simplified for less advanced users. Sharing smart data in the network can support stakeholders along the food system. User-customisable data outputs benefits companies, policy makers, local authorities, and citizens in their search for information about foods. This work integrates knowledge of food science and innovative engineering. The next step will be exploring the potential to integrate blockchain technologies in the demonstrator to increase trust.

7 Appendix

Annex 1A. Virgin olive oil supply chain.

Annex 1B. Step list of virgin olive oil supply chain with definition, input and output. Where there are multiple outputs, the matrix of analysis is marked in bold. The green row highlights the steps that can mainly impact sustainability, covering processing by-products that can be used as secondary raw materials (food and non-food, e.g., cosmetics, nutraceuticals) or for energy production.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX OF ANALYSIS
CULTIVATION AND GROWTH	All stages that concern agronomic practices to make olives growth and keep them healthy until harvest	X	OLIVES
HARVESTING	The process of gathering a ripe crop from olives fields. Can be done after natural fall; by hand, by beating the branches, with shakers, by combing (previously is commonly used to punt canvases on the soil for the reception of the harvested fruits)	OLIVES	OLIVES
POSTHARVESTING	Olives are taken from the nets on the ground and put into bins	OLIVES	OLIVES
TRANSPORT OF OLIVES	Olives are transported to oil mill by olive grower	OLIVES	OLIVES
OLIVE STORAGE	Olives are stored in rigid and ventilated containers in a cool and dry environment	OLIVES	OLIVES
COMBINING DIFFERENT LOADS OF OLIVES	Olives can arrive from different olive's growers and are mixed together	OLIVES	OLIVES
CLEANING	Involves defoliation and washing	OLIVES	OLIVES
SORTING	Discarding any bruised or defective fruit	OLIVES	OLIVES
DEPITTING	Separation of the pits from the olives	OLIVES	OLIVES
extraction	Preparation of the paste. The ideal objective of any extraction method is to extract the largest possible amount of oil without altering its original quality	OLIVES	OLIVE PASTE
CRUSHING	Crushing of olives. The purpose is to disrupt the tissues of the fruit and facilitate release of oil from oil bodies. This step can be done with stone mills, metal tooth grinders, or various kinds of hammermills	OLIVES	OLIVE PASTE (oil-in-water emulsion)
MALAXATION	Mixing of olive paste that allows small oil droplets to combine into larger ones	OLIVE PASTE (oil-in-water emulsion)	OLIVE PASTE (Water-in-oil emulsion)
separation	Separation of olive paste in its components: oil, pomace (solid remains of olive) and vegetation water. It can be obtained with three system: - by pressing, - by centrifugation, - by percolation through selective filtration	OLIVE PASTE (Water-in-oil emulsion)	OLIVE OIL, OLIVE POMACE, VEGETATION WATER
PRESSING	Pressing is carried out with hydraulic electric pumps, cage and column press are open monobloc super presses that allow reaching pressures of 350-500 atmospheres	OLIVE PASTE (Water-in-oil emulsion)	OLIVE MUST (OIL + VEG. WATER), OLIVE POMACE
DECANTATION	Separation of olive oil from water by natural decantation (is the most old method to preserve product); it followed by pouring	OLIVE POMACE, VEG. WATER, OLIVE PASTE	VIRGIN OLIVE OIL , VEG. WATER
PERCOLATION	Percolation is based on the difference in the surface tension between oil and vegetation water. Olive oil percolate goes to centrifuge and in some milling paste goes to 2 phase decanter to recover oil still present	OLIVE PASTE (Water-in-oil emulsion)	OLIVE OIL , OLIVE POMACE OIL
CENTRIFUGATION	It is based on the differences in density of the olive paste constituents (olive oil, water and insoluble solids). The olive paste is subjected to centrifugation in a conical rotating drum with a horizontal axis called DECANTER where Liquid-Solid Separation takes place	OLIVE PASTE (water-in-oil emulsion) + ADDED WATER IN THE 3 PHASE DEC.	OLIVE OIL , VEG. WATER, OLIVE POMACE OR OLIVE OIL AND HUMID OLIVE POMACE
2 AND 3 PHASES DECANTERS	In the three-phase centrifugal decanter, paste is divided into oil, vegetation water and solids (olive pomace), i.e. kernel and pulp fragments During the path to the three-phase centrifugal decanter, water is added to dilute the incoming paste. In the two- phase process, paste instead is separated in oil as a liquid phase and a solid phase composed of fragments and kernels, pulp and vegetation water (humid olive pomace)		
FINAL CENTRIFUGATION	Split olive oil from the other materials. Regardless of the process used for oil extraction, a final centrifugation with lukewarm water is performed to further remove water and small solids from the oil. Output is cleaned oil with less than 0.2% of moisture and volatile matter (% w/w), and less than 0.1% of insoluble impurities in light petroleum (% w/w) This process is carried out in vertical centrifuges that rotate at high speed (6000-7000 rpm)	OLIVE OIL + WATER	VIRGIN OLIVE OIL AND OILY DEPOSIT
PROCESSING WASTE	The by-products are olive mill wastewater (OMW) and/or olive-pomace and, and less importantly, twigs and leaves. The vegetation water can be used in agronomic, energy and industry fields. Olive-pomace can be transformed into olive-pomace oil, biofuel, compost, animal feed, biodiesel, polysaccharides, antioxidants, ceramic materials, etc.	WASTEWATER, OLIVE POMACE	OLIVE-POMACE OIL, AND OTHER
FILTRATION	It is aimed at making the oil clearer and protecting it from premature ageing. Is carried out in two steps: first, the suspended solids are re-moved, and second elimination of humidity gives the oil brilliant aspect. It can be carried out with press filters or spontaneous leaving the product at rest by the action of the force of gravity	OLIVE OIL	FILTERED VOO
OIL STORAGE	At industry keeping oil in sealed stainless steel tanks, with nitrogen blanketing at 15-18 °C. Other processes store oil in bottles or tin cans (or any other appropriated containers) at 15-18 °C	VOO	VOO
OIL BLENDING	Mixing virgin olive oils obtained from different olive varieties to create own unique blend	VOOs	BLEND -MULTI VARIETAL VOO
PACKAGING AND LABELING	Edible Virgin Olive Oil is put into bottles or tin cans and labelled	EDIBLE VOO	VOO PACKED & LABELED
DISTRIBUTION	Distribution of bottles or tin cans tanks using trucks or cargo through various channels to reach the final consumer. These channels are either retailing companies or other processing companies (for ex. canteen or restaurants)	VOO PACKED & LAB.	VOO PACKED & LABELED
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets or supermarkets	VOO PACKED & LAB.	VOO PACKED & LAB.
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home/at restaurant	VOO PACKED & LAB.	VOO PACKED & LAB.
STORAGE	Storage at home or in restaurants, canteens, in clear and dark containers	VOO PACKED & LAB.	VOO PACKED & LAB.
FOOD PREPARATION	Using the oil in food recipes	VOO PACKED & LAB.	VOO READY TO EAT

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Annex 1C.1. The olive milling process's routes (Peri, 2014).

Comment: No 4 (refined olive oil) is edible per se but not commercially available as a food category.

Annex 1C.2. Definition of olive oil related products terms.

DEFINITIONS

VIRGIN OLIVE OILS

Oils obtained from the fruit of the olive tree solely by mechanical or other physical means under conditions that do not lead to alterations in the oil, which have not undergone any treatment other than washing, decantation, centrifugation or filtration, to the exclusion of oils obtained using solvents or using adjuvants having a chemical or biochemical action, or by re-esterification process and any mixture with oils of other kinds.

Classified as follows:

1. EXTRA VIRGIN OLIVE OIL

Virgin olive oil having a maximum free acidity, in terms of oleic acid, of 0,8 g per 100 g, the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...]for this category.

2. VIRGIN OLIVE OIL

Virgin olive oil having a maximum free acidity, in terms of oleic acid, of 2 g per 100 g, the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

3. LAMPANTE OLIVE OIL

Virgin olive oil having a free acidity in terms of oleic acid, of more than 2 g per 100 g, and/or the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

4. REFINED OLIVE OIL

Olive oil obtained by refining virgin olive oil, having a free acidity content expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 0,3 g per 100 g, and the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

5. OLIVE OIL - COMPOSED OF REFINED OLIVE OILS AND VIRGIN OLIVE OILS

Olive oil obtained by blending refined olive oil and virgin olive oil other than lampante olive oil, having a free acidity content expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 1 g per 100 g, and the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...]for this category.

6. CRUDE OLIVE-POMACE OIL

Oil obtained from olive pomace by treatment with solvents or by physical means or oil corresponding to lampante olive oil, except for certain specified characteristics, excluding oil obtained by means of re-esterification and mixtures with other types of oils, and the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

7. REFINED OLIVE-POMACE OIL

Oil obtained by refining crude olive-pomace oil, having free acidity content expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 0,3 g per 100 g, and the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

8. OLIVE-POMACE OIL

Oil obtained by blending refined olive-pomace oil and virgin olive oil other than lampante olive oil, having a free acidity content expressed as oleic acid, of not more than 1 g per 100 g, and the other characteristics of which comply with those laid down by the Commission [...] for this category.

IN GREEN BOXES EDIBLE OILS

Annex XVI REGULATION (EC)
1308/2013 (cons. 2020)

Annex 1D. Catalogue of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the virgin olive oil supply chain.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY										
MATRIX										
STEP	CULTIVATION AND GROWTH	HARVESTING	POSTHARVESTING	TRANSPORT OF OLIVES	OLIVES STORAGE	ARRIVAL AT THE MILL	COMBINING DIFFERENT LOADS OF OLIVES	CLEANING	SORTING	DEPITTING
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	fatty acids (FFAs, SFAs, MUFAs and PUFAs), total polyphenols, tocopherol, secoiridoids (oleuropein, hydroxytyrosol), phytosterols, pigments (carotenoids, chlorophylls), lignans, secoiridoid derivatives, 3,4-DHPEA-AC, monoglycerides and peroxides, DAGs, peroxide value, pH, total CHO, soluble solids, % in oil				micronutrients content, free acidity level, peroxide, K232 value, K270 value, mould	air humidity, free acidity	micronutrients, total polyphenols, secoiridoids, phytosterols, pigments	total polyphenols	olives texture	pits, pit dust
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	climatic and pedoclimatic conditions: e.g., air composition, sun exposure, physical-chemical characteristics (pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC); C total, pE) of soil and trees, irrigation); type and fertilisers content; pruning, pest and disease management	time (t), techniques applied, maturity index, detachment index	Temperature (T), t, mechanical breakages, equipment type and characteristics		storage conditions (T,t)	storage conditions (T,t)	mixing ratio, content in each single load of olives	t, washing water quality and T	machinery efficiency	machinery efficiency
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: GC and GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC, HPLC-DAD, HPLC-UV, UHPLC-MS, Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR), colorimetric methods; non-destructive tests				chemical analysis: atomic spectroscopy (AAS, ICP-AES), titration of free fatty acids, acidimeter, titration with sodium thiosulfate for POV, UV	chemical analysis: titration of free fatty acids, acidimeter	chemical analysis: atomic spectroscopy (AAS, ICP-AES), GC and GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS	chemical analysis: GC, HPLC, CE, CGC, RP-HPLC	non-destructive tests	non-destructive tests
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	agro-meteorological weather stations, agro-meteorological sensors, satellite images, logbook,	manual dynamometer, time logger, logbook	T sensor, time logger, logbook, visual inspection		T sensor, time logger, logbook,	hygrometer, T sensor, time logger	shipping notes	T sensor, time logger, analytical reports	x	x

MATRIX	OLIVES	OLIVE PASTE	MUST	OIL-MUST	OIL	OIL													
STEP	CRUSHING	MALAXATION	EXTRACTION AND SEPARATION	CENTRIFUGATION	FILTRATION	OIL STORAGE	OIL BLENDING	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION				
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	micronutrients, total polyphenols, volatile compounds and pigments, secoiridoids, total DAGs, acidity, homogeneity, non-volatile oxidation products (phenols, hydroxylated fatty acids), organoleptic characteristics					1,2-DAGs, tocopherol, peroxide value, lipid oxidation products (i.e. hydroperoxides, conjugated dienes and trienes), K232 value, K270 value, organoleptic characteristics	tot polyphenols, volatile compounds and pigments, secoiridoids, organoleptic characteristics		tot polyphenols, volatile compounds and pigments, secoiridoids, organoleptic characteristics										
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	T, t, equipment type and characteristics, machinery efficiency, oxidation, handling practices and cleaning efficiency, chemical and solid residues, degree of emulsification produced in the crushing stage, extension of cell damage					T, t, humidity, light, enzymes, metalloproteins, impurities and solid residues	x	package's materials and integrity, machinery efficiency, light	T, t, light, humidity, package's materials and integrity										cooking method (T, t)
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: atomic spectroscopy (AAS, ICP-AES), GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, Headspace-Gas Chromatography					chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC, UV spectrophotometer	chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC, UV spectrophotometer)		chemical analysis: GC, HPLC, UV, spectrophotometry/ HPLC, Headspace-Gas Chromatography, panels for sensory analysis										
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, time logger, analytical reports, logbook, haccp manual, logbook					T ambient sensor, time logger, humidity monitor	x	logbook, light sensor	T sensor, time logger, humidity monitor, UV Light Sensor, visual inspection										

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the virgin olive oil supply chain.

SAFETY										
MATRIX	OLIVES									
STEP	CULTIVATION AND GROWTH	HARVESTING	POSTHARVESTING	TRANSPORT OF OLIVES	OLIVES STORAGE	ARRIVAL AT THE MILL	COMBINING DIFFERENT LOADS OF OLIVES	CLEANING	SORTING	DEPITTING
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical: PHAs, pesticides, toxic and potentially toxic elements; biological: mycotoxins, moulds, physical contaminants: radionuclides	microbial growth and fermentation by bacteria, yeasts, moulds	mixing the good olives with broken or contaminated ones, chemical: phthalate esters; biological: yeast, flies' larvae, moulds; physical contaminants: foreign materials				chemical and biological contaminants: mixing the good olives with broken or contaminated ones	chemical: pesticides; biological contaminants: mixing the good olives with broken or contaminated ones; physical: dust, leaves, sand	x	x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS	pedoclimatic conditions e.g., physical-chemical characteristics of soil (pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC); C total, PE), environmental pollution, physiopathological factors, biocides and plant protection products, irrigation water	t, harvesting system (breaking and bruising, mud)	equipment, storage and transport conditions (T, t, airflow, rain, sun), mechanical breakages, handling efficiency, cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of food contact material (FCM)				handling efficiency	washing water quality, cleaning efficiency	x	x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: GC-MS, HPLC-MS, HPLC-MS/MS, UFLC-MS/MS, thin-layer chromatography (TLC), HPLC-FLD, GC-MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, DNA-based techniques	chemical analysis: LC-MS, HPLC-DAD-QTOFMS for Fungal Metabolites Analysis, DNA-based techniques	chemical analysis (LC-MS, HPLC-DAD-QTOFMS for Fungal Metabolites Analysis), DNA-based techniques, visual inspection				chemical analysis: LC-MS, HPLC-DAD-QTOFMS for Fungal Metabolites Analysis, DNA-based techniques, visual inspection	chemical analysis (LC-MS, HPLC-DAD-QTOFMS for Fungal Metabolites Analysis, Liquid-liquid extraction techniques coupled with solid-phase extraction clean up -GC, Ion-Trap GC-MS), DNA-based techniques; visual inspection, nondestructive tests	x	x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	agro-meteorological weather stations, logbook, gas sensor, agricultural drone, satellite images, chemical analysis	time logger, logbook, microbiological analysis	T sensor, logbook, shipping notes				shipping notes, logbook	chemical analysis	x	x

MATRIX	OLIVES	OLIVE PASTE	MUST	OIL-MUST	OIL	FILTERED OIL	OIL								
STEP	CRUSHING	MALAXATION	EXTRACTION AND SEPARATION	CENTRIFUGATION	FILTRATION	OIL STORAGE	OIL BLENDING	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical: trihalomethanes, mineral hydrocarbons; physical contaminants: metals					chemical: phthalate esters, mineral hydrocarbons, physical contaminants: impurities and solid residues		chemical: phthalate esters, BPA, mineral hydrocarbon; physical: foreign matters	biological: moulds, bacteria, yeasts						chemical: acrolein, biological: pathogenic and spoilage organisms
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS	T, t, cleaning and disinfection programs efficiency, integrity of food contact material (FCM), food contact with the lubricating oils of processing plants and machinery (bulldozer motor oil, lubricating oils used in augers, belt conveyors)					cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of FCM		cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of FCM, printing ink ingredients	humidity, T, t						smoke point, cooking method (T, t), integrity of FCM, cleaning and sanitizing procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: HPLC, HPLC-GC-FID, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS					chemical analysis: HPLC, HPLC-GC-FID	visual inspection, nondestructive tests	chemical analysis: HPLC, HPLC-GC-FID; nondestructive tests	visual inspection, nondestructive tests						chemical analysis (LC-MS, GC-MS, liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME), GC-MS, visual inspection
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual, logbook,					T ambient sensor, humidity sensor, light sensor, aroma sensor, inspection (infrared, x-ray, etc.)	HACCP manual	visual inspection	T sensor, time logger, humidity sensor						T sensor

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the virgin olive oil supply chain.

AUTHENTICITY/ TRANSPARENCY		OLIVES								
MATRIX										
STEP	CULTIVATION AND GROWTH	HARVESTING	POSTHARVESTING	TRANSPORT OF OLIVES	OLIVES STORAGE	ARRIVAL AT THE MILL	COMBINING DIFFERENT LOADS OF OLIVES	CLEANING	SORTING	DEPITTING
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	isotopic ratios, rare earth elements, organic compounds (fatty acids, triglycerides, volatile compounds, pigments profiles), minerals, genomic profiles				x		isotopic ratios, rare earth elements, organic compounds (fatty acids, triglycerides, volatile compounds, pigments profiles), minerals, genomic profiles		x	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS	cultivar, latitude, longitude, rainfall, distance from sea, sun exposition, physical-chemical characteristics of soil (pH, cation exchange capacity (CEC); C total, pE) fertilisers use				x		olives loads provenance, cultivar, latitude, longitude, rainfall, distance from sea, sun exposition, physical-chemical characteristics of soil, fertilisers use		x	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC, GC/C/IRMS, DNA-based techniques, spectroscopy (e.g., nuclear magnetic resonance, mass spectrometry, NRM); electronic noses				x		chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC, GC/C/IRMS; DNA-based techniques, spectroscopy (e.g., nuclear magnetic resonance, mass spectrometry, NMR); electronic noses		x	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	logbook, drone, satellite images, agro-meteorological station, chemical analysis				x		logbook, disciplinary of production (for certificated products)		x	

MATRIX	OLIVES	OLIVE PASTE	MUST	OIL-MUST	OIL	FILTERED OIL	OIL								
STEP	CRUSHING	MALAXATION	EXTRACTION AND SEPARATION	CENTRIFUGATION	FILTRATION	OIL STORAGE	OIL BLENDING	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST			x		glycosides of leaves; sterols, fatty acid alkyl esters (FAAEs), diacylglycerols (DAGs), degradation products of chlorophylls and phenolic compounds - e.g., pyropheophytins (PPPs); volatile compounds	x	origin of olives used: isotopic ratios, rare earth elements, micronutrients, pigments profiles, genomic profiles		x			origin of olives used: isotopic ratios, rare earth elements, micronutrients, pigments profiles, genomic profiles		x	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS			x		presence of leaves, refined oils	x	cultivar, latitude, longitude, rainfall, distance from sea, sun exposition, physical-chemical characteristics of soil, fertilisers use		x			cultivar, latitude, longitude, rainfall, distance from sea, sun exposition, physical-chemical characteristics of soil, fertilisers use		x	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING			x		chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC	x	chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, GC/FID, LC-MS/MS, HPLC		x			chemical analysis: DNA-based (e.g., microsatellite DNA, random amplified polymorphic DNA); chromatography; spectroscopy (e.g., NMR, MS); visual inspection		x	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING			x		logbook, disciplinary of production (for certificated products), inspection (infrared, x-ray, etc.)	x	logbook, disciplinary of production (for certificated products)		x			x		x	

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

Annex 2A. Milk supply chain.

Annex 2B. Steps list of milk supply chain with definitions, inputs and outputs.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT and MATRIX OF ANAUSYS
FEEDING AND FARMING PRACTICES	If concerns all practices applied for maintenance of a good status of the animal (e.g., the choice of the type of forage, forage quantity)	FORAGE	RAW MILK
HAND/MACHINE MILKING	Hand milking: operator hand presses the milk out of the teat cistem and the milk is collected in pails and poured through a strainer Machine milking: The milking machine sucks the milk out of the teat by vacuum	RAW MILK	RAW MILK
CHILLING MILK	Milk is chilled quickly to about 4°C immediately after it leaves the cow	RAW MILK	RAW MILK CHILLED
RAW MILK COLLECTION AND HAULING	The milk is brought in churns of various sizes from the farm, or collecting centre, to the dairy for processing or to markets	CHILL RAW MILK	CHILL RAW MILK
STORAGE	Refrigerated storage at 4°C in tanks, silo tanks or in their packaging (depending on the phase)	CHILL RAW MILK	CHILL RAW MILK
CENTRIFUGATION/CLARIFICATION	The purpose is to remove from the milk all foreign material (organic and inorganic material, somatic cells, microorganisms and their protein agglomerates), which may have entered milk during milking, treatment or transport. Centrifugal separation can be applied to remove bacteria as well as their spores ("bactofugation")	RAW MILK	MILK
DECREAMING	Is the mechanical separation of milk into cream and skim milk by means of centrifugal forces	MILK	SKIMMED MILK
HOMOGENIZATION	Is not always part of the treatment, it is used only when it is advantageous for further processing. Is the disintegration of particles in which uniformly or non-uniformly distributed phases of a liquid reach a higher level of mixing and the distribution level stabilizes	DECREAMED MILK	HOMOGENIZED MILK
FAT STANDARDIZATION	Fat standardization is the adjustment of a predefined fat content (in %) in milk. It can be done by blending precalculated quantities of whole milk and skim milk in silos, or by using standardization facilities	HOMOGENIZED MILK	WHOLE/SEMI-SKIMMED MILK
PROCESSING WASTE	The fat residues can be used to standardize fat content in other milk products or can be used to make cream, acid cream, greek yogurts, butter, buttermilk, etc	FAT RESIDUES, etc	DAIRY PRODUCTS
ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	Vitamins, fibre, minerals, essential fatty acids, can be added in order to "enrich" or "fortify" the milk, so as to add or emphasise particular nutritional characteristics	MILK	ENRICHED MILK
HEAT TREATMENT	Heat treatment is nearly always applied, and it induces numerous chemical and other changes, the extent of which depends on temperature and duration of heating. Depending on temperature and duration can be distinguished: pasteurization, processing with UHT, sterilizing raw milk or microfiltration	MILK	UHT/ PASTEURIZED/MICROFILTERED/STERILIZED MILK
MICROFILTRATION	The system, which combines a mechanical treatment with a thermal one, consists in separating the lipid fraction of the milk, which cannot be microfiltered, and in thermally treating it at 120-140 ° C. The skimmed milk is instead filtered through a porous membrane (1 µm in diameter). Subsequently the two fractions are mixed and pasteurized (72-80 ° C)	MILK	MICROFILTERED
PASTEURIZATION	The minimum pasteurisation conditions are those having bactericidal effects equivalent to heating every particle of the milk to 72°C for 15 s (continuous flow pasteurisation) or 63°C for 30 min (batch pasteurisation)	MILK	PASTEURIZED MILK
STERILIZATION	Consist of treating milk at 109-115 °C for 20-45 minutes.	MILK	STERILIZED MILK
ULTRA-HIGH-TEMPERATURE PROCESSING	Ultra-high-temperature processing (UHT) of milk consists of treating the milk at 138–145 °C for 2–10 s	MILK	UHT MILK
COOLING	It is done immediately after the heating process. The final temperatures are selected as a function of the foreseen utilization of the cooled milk. Fresh milk require cooling to <6 °C	MILK	CHILL MILK
INTERMEDIATE STORAGE	It is done in vessels and is made to guarantee a continuous supply during filling, to separate the filling operation from the manufacturing operation, to monitor milk's quality and for standardization of the fat content if standardization is not done during the decreaming stage	CHILL MILK	CHILL MILK
FILLING, PACKAGING AND LABELING	Milk processed is inserted into pack/container previously sterilized and labelled	MILK PACKED AND LABELED	MILK PACKED AND LABELED
DISTRIBUTION	Distribution using trucks or cargo through various channels to reach the final consumer. These channels are either retailing companies or other processing companies (for ex. canteen or restaurants)	MILK PACKED AND LAB.	MILK PACKED AND LAB.
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets and supermarkets	MILK PACKED AND LAB.	MILK PACKED AND LAB.
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home/at restaurant by car or truck	MILK PACKED AND LAB.	MILK PACKED AND LAB.
STORAGE	Storage at home or in restaurants or canteens	MILK PACKED AND LAB.	MILK PACKED AND LAB.
FOOD PREPARATION	Using milk in food recipes	MILK PACKED AND LAB.	MILK AS SUCH OR IN COMBINATION WITH OTHERS INGREDIENTS

Annex 2C.1. Definitions for milk related terms.

DEFINITIONS

RAW MILK: milk which has not been heated above 40 °C or subjected to treatment having equivalent effect.

MILK: "Milk" means exclusively the normal mammary secretion obtained from one or more milkings without either addition thereto or extraction therefrom.

However, the term "milk" may be used:

- (a) for milk treated without altering its composition or for milk the fat content of which is standardised under Part IV;
- (b) in association with a word or words to designate the type, grade, origin and/or intended use of such milk or to describe the physical treatment or the modification in composition to which it has been subjected, provided that the modification is restricted to an addition and/or withdrawal of natural milk constituents.

[...] only the following modifications shall be allowed:

- (a) in order to meet the fat contents laid down for drinking milk, modification of the natural fat content by the removal or addition of cream or the addition of whole milk, semi-skimmed milk or skimmed milk;
- (b) enrichment of milk with milk proteins, mineral salts or vitamins, in accordance with Reg. (EC) 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council;
- (c) reduction of the lactose content by conversion to glucose and galactose.

Part III Annex VII Reg. (EU) n. 1308/2013 - Cons. version: 7/12/2021

UHT MILK: UHT treatment is normally in the range of 135 to 150 C in combination with appropriate holding times necessary to achieve commercial sterility. Other equivalent conditions can be established through consultation with an official or officially recognised authority.

MICROFILTERED MILK: removed of microbial cells, clumps and somatic cells by recirculation over a microfilter. Synergy in combination with heat treatment.

PASTEURISED MILK: The application of heat to milk and liquid milk products aimed at reducing the number of any pathogenic micro-organisms to a level at which they do not constitute a significant health hazard.

STERILISED MILK: Commercial sterilization is a microbiocidal control measure that can be obtained by various heat treatments, the most common and [validated] methods being UHT (ultra high temperature) processing in combination with aseptic packaging or In-container Sterilization.

FAO, 2004

Annex 2C.2 Definitions for different types of milk based on fat content.

Types of milk based on fat content

WHOLE MILK: heat-treated milk which, with respect to fat content, meets one of the following requirements:

- standardised whole milk: milk with a fat content of at least 3,50 % (m/m). However, Member States may provide for an additional category of whole milk with a fat content of 4,00 % (m/m) or above

- non-standardised whole milk: milk with a fat content that has not been altered since the milking stage either by the addition or removal of milk fats or by mixture with milk the natural fat content of which has been altered. However, the fat content may not be less than 3,50 % (m/m)

SEMI-SKIMMED MILK: heat-treated milk whose fat content has been reduced to at least 1,50 % (m/m) and at most 1,80 % (m/m);

SKIMMED-MILK: heat-treated milk whose fat content has been reduced to not more than 0,50 % (m/m).

Part IV Annex VII Reg. (EU) n. 1308/2013 - Cons. version: 29/12/2020

Annex 2D. Catalogue of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Interest monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the milk supply chain.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY									
MATRIX	RAW MILK					SKIMMED MILK	HOMOGENIZED MILK	WHOLE/SEMI-SKIMMED MILK	
STEP	FEEDING AND FARMING PRACTICES	HAND/MACHINE MILKING	CHILLING MILK	RAW MILK COLLECTION AND HAULING	STORAGE	CENTRIFUGATION/CLARIFICATION	DECREAMING	HOMOGENISATION	FAT STANDARDISATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	fatty acids (PUFA), total phenolic compounds (TPCs), vitamins (A, B, D, E, C), provitamins (β-carotene, ergosterol), minerals	acidity, salts balance, proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes, casein concentration and total protein		x		somatic cells	residual fat content in skim milk, free fatty acids, degradation of milk fat globule membranes (MFGM)	free fatty acids, degradation of milk fat globule membranes (MFGM)	
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	feed composition, climatic and pedoclimatic conditions, cow health status	breed, parity (n° of offspring), stage of lactation, milking frequency		x		machinery efficiency	T, machinery efficiency	fat content, T, pressure, machinery efficiency and stress	T, machinery efficiency
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: LC-MS/MS, GC-MS, UPLC, HPLC, HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF, UHPLC, NIRS, MIR, Folin-Ciocalteu method for TPCs, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS	chemical analysis: capillary electrophoresis, titration, infrared spectrophotometer, method for determination of lipolytic activity (MeDeLi), Titrimetric and colorimetric method, Kjeldahl method		x		somatic cells count	chemical analysis: Geber method, the Rose-Gottlieb method, the Babcock method, the Tesa method, Mojonnier method, Dielectric Property Measurement, Proteomic analysis, CG-FID, GC-MS	x	chemical analysis: Geber method, the Rose-Gottlieb method, the Babcock method, the Tesa method, Mojonnier method, Dielectric Property Measurement, Proteome analysis, CG-FID, GC-MS
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	farm register, logbook, drone, agro-meteorological weather stations, precision farming	logbook		x		logbook		x	T sensor, logbook

MATRIX	MILK	UHT/PASTEURIZED/ MICROFILTERED/ STERILIZED MILK	PACKED MILK							MILK		
STEP	ADDITION OF FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENTS	HEAT TREATMENT	COOLING	INTERMEDIATE STORAGE	FILLING, PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	fiber, omega-3, minerals (calcium), fiber, vegetable protein	Lipoprotein lipase (LPL), short-chain fatty acids, vitamins, Maillard reaction products (furosine), essential aminoacids, organoleptic characteristics	x		oxidation of fats, aminoacids, vitamins, Maillard reaction products (furosine), lactulose, organoleptic characteristics							
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	x	T, t, machinery efficiency, microorganisms	x		T, t, humidity, exposure to light, package's materials and integrity							cooking method (T, t)
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	x	chemical analysis: method for determination of lipolytic activity (MeDeLi), Titrimetric and colorimetric method, Kjeldahl method, LC-MS/MS, GC-MS, UPLC, HPLC	x		chemical analysis: GC, GC-MS, HPLC, colorimetric-enzymatic method							x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	x	T sensor, time logger	x		T sensor, time logger, humidity sensor, UV light sensor, visual inspection							T sensor, time logger

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Interest monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the milk supply chain.

SAFETY										
MATRIX	RAW MILK						DECREAMED MILK	HOMOGENIZED MILK	WHOLE/SKIMMED/SEMI-SKIMMED MILK	
STEP	FEEDING AND FARMING PRACTICES	HAND/MACHINE MILKING	CHILLING MILK	RAW MILK COLLECTION AND HAULING	STORAGE	CENTRIFUGATION/CLARIFICATION	DECREAMING	HOMOGENIZATION	FAT STANDARDIZATION	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	brominated flame retardants, PAHs, organochlorines, perfluorinated substances, dioxins, antibiotic residues, antiparasitic drugs, painkillers, other drugs (Chloramphenicol), toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms (E. Coli), spores of butyric acid bacteria, mycotoxins, viruses; foreign matters	disinfectants (iodine, quaternary ammonium compound (QAC) residues, TCM residues and chlorinated byproducts), phthalate esters; total bacteria, somatic cells, pathogenic and spoilage organisms (Staphylococcus aureus, E. coli, mastitis bacteria); foreign matters (metal, plastic, glass, rubber, wood parts, sand/soil, stones, hair)	disinfectants, toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms, metabolic products and enzymes; foreign matters		toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms, metabolic products and enzymes	phthalate esters, toxic and potentially toxic elements; bacteria, spores and somatic cells	disinfectants, toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms (psychrotrophs), metabolic products			
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	climatic and pedoclimatic conditions, feed composition, contaminants on feed and water, fertilisers content and type, pest and disease management, cow health status, veterinary medicines	cleaning procedures efficiency (environment, animals, operators); integrity of food contact materials (FCM)	T, t, cleaning and disinfection programs efficiency, machinery efficiency, integrity of FCM		T (ambient), t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of FCM	machinery efficiency, integrity of FCM	T (milk), t, machinery efficiency and hygiene, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM			
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, GC, UHPLC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, TLC, Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), Soxhlet apparatus, Solid-phase extraction (SPE), Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), solid-phase microextraction (SPME), hollow liquid phase microextraction and fluorescence detection (UV/FL) and fluorescence detector (FLD); microbiological analysis (PCR-ELISA system, RT-PCR, California Mastitis Test (CMT), Cultural methods, diffusion assays, enzymatic colourimetric assays, Immunoassays, ELISA), somatic cells count nondestructive tests									
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	agro-meteorological weather stations, gas sensor, farm register, logbook, precision farming	HACCP manual	T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual		T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual		T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual			

MATRIX	MILK	UHT/PASTEURIZED/ MICROFILTERED/ STERILIZED MILK	PACKED MILK								MILK	
STEP	ADDITION OF FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENTS	HEAT TREATMENT	COOLING	INTERMEDIATE STORAGE	FILLING, PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	x	carboxymethyl-sine (CML), toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms, vegetative pathogens, spores of pathogens		toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms	phthalates, phthalate esters, 2-printing ink ingredients (isopropyl thioxanthone (ITX) and 2-ethylhexyl-4-dimethylaminobenzoate), toxic and potentially toxic elements; pathogenic and spoilage organisms	toxic and potentially toxic elements (phtalates, BPA); pathogenic and spoilage organisms					pathogenic and spoilage organisms	
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	x	T (milk), t, integrity of FCM , cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency,		T (ambient), t, cleaning procedures efficiency	T, t, package material, machinery efficiency, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, printing ink ingredients	refrigeration system control efficiency (T), t, humidity, exposure to sunlight, integrity of FCM					T, t, humidity, cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of FCM	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, GC, UHPLC-MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, TLC, Liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), Soxhlet apparatus, Solid-phase extraction (SPE), Pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), solid-phase microextraction (SPME), hollow liquid phase microextraction (HF-LPME), GC/FID, GC/MS, HPLC equipped with ultraviolet and fluorescence detection (UV/FL) and fluorescence detector (FLD); microbiological analysis (PCR-ELISA system, RT-PCR, California Mastitis Test (CMT), Cultural methods, diffusion assays, enzymatic colourimetric assays, Immunoassays, ELISA), somatic cells count, nondestructive tests											
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	x	T sensor, time logger		T sensor, time logger	HACCP manual, logbook	T ambient sensor, time logger, humidity sensor, sunlight sensor, HACCP manual					T sensor, time logger	

steps in italics are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

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Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameters of Interest monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the milk supply chain.

AUTHENTICITY/ TRANSPARENCY	RAW MILK						DECREAMED MILK	HOMOGENIZED MILK	WHOLE/SKIMMED/SEMI-SKIMMED MILK
MATRIX									
STEP	FEEDING AND FARMING PRACTICES	HAND/MACHINE MILKING	CHILLING MILK	RAW MILK COLLECTION AND HAULING	STORAGE	CENTRIFUGATION/CLARIFICATION	DECREAMING	HOMOGENIZATION	FAT STANDARDIZATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	terpenes (sesquiterpenes), carotenes and fatty acids, isotope ratios, lactones or phytynes or flavonoids, phenolic compounds, genomic profiles					x			
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	cow diets (botanical type of forage or silage eaten), latitude, longitude, animal breed					x			
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques					x			
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	farm register, GPS sensor					x			

MATRIX	MILK	UHT/PASTEURIZED/ MICROFILTERED/ STERILIZED MILK	PACKED MILK								MILK	
STEP	ADDITION OF FUNCTIONAL INGREDIENTS	HEAT TREATMENT	COOLING	INTERMEDIATE STORAGE	FILLING, PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	DISTRIBUTION	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	x	x	x		terpenes (sesquiterpenes), fatty acids, stable isotope ratios, lactones or phytynes or flavonoids, genomic profiles		x		terpenes (sesquiterpenes), fatty acids, stable isotope ratios, lactones or phytynes or flavonoids, genomic profiles, lactulose and furosine	x		x
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	x	x	x		cow diets (botanical type of forage or silage eaten), latitude, longitude, specific animal breed, zoologic origin							x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	x	x	x		chemical analysis (e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method), DNA-based techniques							x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	x	x	x		logbook							x

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

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Annex 3A. Fishery products supply chain.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863059.

Annex 3B. Steps list of fishery products supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
CATCHING	Fishery products are caught	X	FISH
TRANSHIPMENT AT SEA PROCESSOR	Fishery products caught are transferred at a sea processor. A sea processor is like a industry	X	FISH
REFRIGERATION	Fish is kept at ~0° C in refrigerators with or without adding crushed ice or in absence of refrigerators covering or alternating the fish with shredded ice	FISH	REFRIGERATED FISH
CLEANING, WASHING, FILLETING	1) Clean the fish well and cut off the fins, scrape off the scales and remove gills, make a slit in the belly and remove all the internal organs (this is also known as gutting of the fish) 2) Wash them in running water to remove all the blood and any physical impurities. 3) Filletting is the neat removal of the flesh of the fish from its skeleton to yield sections of fish flesh free from skin and bone	FISH	CLEANED FISH OR FILLET
PROCESSING WASTE	Fish residues can be transformed into flour, oil, paste and fish meal by the same industry or by other ones	FISH RESIDUES	FLOUR, OIL, PASTE, FISH MEAL
VACUUM PACKING	Packaging in which the atmosphere surrounding the fish is different from the normal composition of air	CLEANED FISH OR FILLET	PACKED FISH
SHARP FREEZING	A method for preservation of foods by rapid freezing until the product core temperature reaches -18 ° C. Freezing done in such a way that the zone of maximum crystallization is passed through rapidly and the freezing is complete only when the average temperature reaches -18°C	CLEANED FISH OR FILLET	FROZEN FISH
QUICK FREEZING	The quick freezing process shall not be regarded as complete unless and until the product temperature has reached -18°C or colder at the thermal centre after thermal stabilization	CLEANED FISH OR FILLET	FROZEN FISH
GLAZING	Application of a protective layer of ice formed at the surface of a frozen product by spraying it with, or dipping it into, clean seawater, potable water, or potable water with approved additives, as appropriate	CLEANED FISH OR FILLET	GLAZED FISH
PACKAGING AND LABELLING	Wrapping products and putting them in boxes; 'labelling' means any words, particulars, trade marks, brand name, pictorial matter or symbol relating to a food and placed on any packaging, document, notice, label, ring or collar accompanying or referring to such food	FRESH, FROZEN, GLAZED FISH	PACKED AND LABELED FISH
STORAGE	Cold storage except for cannery products	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
LANDING	As the fishing vessel reaches the harbour, fishes are unloaded and weighed	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
TRANSPORT	Vehicle refrigerated or not depending on type of items transported	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
AIRLINES	Airlines prefers refrigerant gel pack than ice	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
PROCESSING COMPANIES	Companies that prepared fish for commercial uses (evisceration, filletting, smoking, etc)	X	PROCESSED AND PACKED FISH
COLD STORAGE	In refrigerators or in freezer	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
CANNERY	A type of processing company where the final product is fish can	PACKED&LAB. FISH	CANNED FISH
AUCTION MARKETS	Auction Market is a stage for buyers and sellers where they can trade stocks by making competing bids and offers	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
WHOLESALE OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	Wholesale is the business of selling of goods in large quantities and at low prices to shops and business; Retail distribution is the sale of goods individually or in small quantities to consumers	X	PACKED&LAB. FISH
LOCAL MARKET/FISHING CO-OPERATIVES	Marketing practices that sell the products in the vicinity of where they are produced		
DISTRIBUTION	Distribution using trucks or cargo through various channels to reach the final consumer. These channels are either retailing companies or other processing companies (for ex. canteen or restaurants)		
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets and supermarkets		
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home by car or at restaurant/canteen by van		
FOOD PREPARATION	Using seafood in food recipes	PACKED&LAB. FISH	FISH READY TO EAT

Annex 3C. Definitions related to fishery products.

DEFINITIONS

Fishery products= all seawater or freshwater animals (except for live bivalve molluscs, live echinoderms, live tunicates and live marine gastropods, and all mammals, reptiles and frogs) whether wild or farmed and including all edible forms, parts and products of such animals. (REG CE n.853/2004 (cons.2021))

Fresh fishery products= unprocessed fishery products, whether whole or prepared, including products packaged under vacuum or in a modified atmosphere, that have not undergone any treatment to ensure preservation other than chilling.

Prepared fishery products= means unprocessed fishery products that have undergone an operation affecting their anatomical wholeness, such as gutting, heading, slicing, filleting, and chopping.

Freezer vessel= any vessel on board which freezing of fishery products is carried out, where appropriate after preparatory work such as bleeding, heading, gutting and removal of fins and, where necessary, followed by wrapping or packaging.

Factory vessel= any vessel on board which fishery products undergo one or more of the following operations followed by wrapping or packaging and, if necessary, chilling or freezing: filleting, slicing, skinning, shelling, shucking, mincing or processing.

Aquaculture= according to Regulation CE n.762/2008 (cons. 2014), aquaculture is defined in Article 3 of Regulation CE n.1198/2006 (cons. 2013) as the rearing or cultivation of aquatic organisms using techniques designed to increase the production of the organisms in question beyond the natural capacity of the environment; the organisms remain the property of a natural or legal person throughout the rearing or culture stage, up to and including harvesting.

Mariculture= by mariculture is understood that the cultivation of the end product takes place in seawater, such as fjords, inshore and open waters and inland seas in which the salinity generally exceeds 20‰. Earlier stages in the life cycle of these aquatic organisms may be spent in brackishwater or freshwater.

Sources: Reg. (EC) 853/2004 (cons. 01/01/2021), FAO and WHO 2020; EFSA 2015; Reg. (EC) 762/2008 (cons. 10/01/2014); Reg (EC) n. 1198/2006 (cons. 01/07/2013)

Annex 3.1A Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) aquaculture supply chain.

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Annex 3.1B. Steps list of Atlantic salmon aquaculture supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
SALMON FEEDING	Feed are made of granulates composed of flour, oil, vitamins, pigment colours and where needed veterinary drugs is added to the meal.	FLOUR, OIL, VITAMINS, ETC.	FEED
BREEDING	The initial phase of the salmon farming cycle takes place in fresh water. The eggs are extracted from the females and mixed with the sperm taken from the male to be fertilized. They are then placed in an incubator tank.	SPERM AND GAMETES	EGGS
JUVENILE SALMON PRODUCER	The rearing of the fry takes place in two phases. The first phase, in cages, lasts from 4 to 6 weeks, until the larva has got rid of its yolk sac and becomes a parr	EGGS	JUVENILE SALMON
SMOLT PRODUCER	the parr is transferred to a freshwater tank (or to a floating cage in a lake), where it remains for one to two years until become smolt	JUVENILE SALMON	SMOLT
SALMON FARMING	it need cold water temperatures varying between 8°C and 14°C. the farmed salmon are transported to seawater cages where remain for 2 years	SMOLT	SALMON
GRADING	Normal grading procedure either involves passing grading grids, which the smaller fish can swim through or pumping fish across a gradin grid. Sweep net with screen are used in cage farms and underwater in land-based farms	SALMON	SALMON CLASSIFIED BY SIZE
STARVING	To ensure that gut contents are evacuated. Starving time depends on fish size and temperature. For Salmon lasts for one to two weeks and even a longer period	SALMON	SALMON
CROWDING	Enables to lift fish more easily out of the water. Time should be limited and should never exceed 2 hours	SALMON	SALMON
TRANSPORT	Farmed fish usually are transported in a well boat or in a truck with tanks. Fish are transferred directly into slaughtering or are kept alive for few days in a pre-slaughter tank or cage	SALMON	SALMON
CHILLING LIVE FISH	In some slaughter houses farmed fish are chilled alive before slaughtering. It reduce muscle T close to 0°C slows down the microbiological, chemical and biochemical decomposition processes. Farm fish need to be slowly chilled down	SALMON	ALIVE SALMON CHILLED
STUNNING/KILLING	The animal is first stunned to make it insensible to pain. Death is then induced by various methods that include bleeding, stopping the heart, or preventing access to oxygen. This stages can occur together. Percussive stunning devices are becoming widespread within salmon industry	SALMON	SALMON KILLED
REFRIGERATION	Fish is chilled quickly in a cooling tub (at 0°) and kept at low T throughout processing line to slow down the microbiological, chemical and biochemical decomposition processes	SALMON KILLED	WHOLE SALMON
CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	It is recommended to cut the gills. Is only applicable to medium to large species. Should be bled as soon as possible for a minimum of 20-30 min	SALMON KILLED	GUTTED SALMON
GUTTING	To prevent autolytic spoilage rather than bacterial spoilage. The gutting of the body cavity, removal of guts and kidney tissue and vacuum suction can be performed in multi-application machines.	SALMON KILLED	GUTTED SALMON
CLEANING	The fish should be washed thoroughly with clean, cold running fresh water or sea water to clean the surfaces from digestive enzymes, blood, spoilage organism and remaining visceral matter	GUTTED SALMON	CLEANED SALMON
SORTING AND GRADING	Standards establish the characteristic and acceptable default which permit fish to be sorted into categories of equal market value	CLEANED SALMON	SALMON CLASSIFIED BY STARNARDS
BEHEADING	mechanized or manual process	CLEANED SALMON	GUTTED SALMON
FILETTING AND SKINNING	The flesh of a fish has been cut or sliced away from the bone by cutting lengthwise along one side of the fish parallel to the backbone; skin removal	CLEANED SALMON	FILLET AND SKINNED SALMON
PROCESSING WASTE	Fish residues can be transformed into flour, oil, paste and fish meal	FISH RESIDUES	FLOUR, OIL, PASTE, FISH MEAL
FREEZING	From the grader, the salmon was transported by pallet truck in containers. After stacking in racks, the salmon was placed in freeze tunnels.	CLEANED SALMON	FREEZED SALMON
ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	Some additives as sodium, sodium tripolyphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates, can be added to maintain the nutritional quality, the shelf-life of fish, and to enhance its colours	FREEZED OR FRESH SALMON	PACKED AND LABELED SALMON

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Steps list (continued) of Atlantic salmon aquaculture supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs and descriptions of product's typologies.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
PACKAGING AND LABELLING	Wrapping products and putting them in boxes; 'labelling' means any words, particulars, trade marks, brand name, pictorial matter or symbol relating to a food and placed on any packaging, document, notice, label, ring or collar accompanying or referring to such food	FREEZED OR REFRIGERATED SALMON	PACKED AND LABELED SALMON
WHOLE FISH	Pack in EPS boxes with ice. EPS is expanded polystyrene, it is an aggregate, non-toxic material that does not allow development of microorganisms and maintains the organoleptic characteristics of fish. ensure that the fresh and frozen fish are kept cool and well protected in order to preserve the same freshness over longer periods no matter the external conditions		
GUTTED FRESH FISH	Gutted fresh packed in boxes with ice		
FRESH FILLET	Fresh fillet packed in boxes with ice		
FROZEN SALMON	Frozen salmon (e.g., whole, beheading, fillets) is packed in boxes, labelled and strapped. After palletizing, pallets are transported to freezer storage		
UNPACKING	Removing the pack	PACKED SALM	SALMON
THAWING	defrosting	FROST SALM.	DEFROST SALMON
DRY/BRINING SALTING	There are basically three methods of drying fish. The common and traditional method being sun drying which is done by utilizing the atmospheric conditions viz., temperature, humidity and airflow. In recent times, the controlled artificial dehydration of fish has been developed so that fish drying can be carried out under controlled conditions, regardless of weather conditions. Dry salting technique, in which fillets salted by hand with refined salt left for 6h at 12 °C. The brine salting technique used saturated brine maintained at 12°C in which the fillets were placed	DEFROST SALMON	DRIED SALMON
RINSING	Wash with clean water (15°C) on grids and stored in a cold room at 2°C until smoking	SALMON	SALMON WHASHED
SMOKING	In the mechanical smoking the smoke is generated outside the smoking chamber and by artificial ventilation forced to flow around the fish; Cold smoking is done at T below 40°C. Hot smoking Temperature is above 60 °C	RINSED SALMON	SMOKED SALMON
COOLING	The fish is placed in the blast chiller at a temperature of 0 ° C	SMOKED SALM	COOLED SALMON
SLICING AND CUTTING	cutting into flat pieces or In small pieces	COOLED SALM	CUTTED SALMON
VACUUM-PACKED SMOKED SALMON	it is vacuum packed in different cuts. Fish processed is inserted into pack/container previously sterilized and labelled		
BRINE SALTING	The process of placing fish in brine for a period of sufficient length for the fish tissue to absorb a specific quantity of salt. CAC/RCP 52-2003	SALMON	BRINED SALMON
CLEANING	The fish should be washed thoroughly with clean, cold running fresh water or sea water to clean the surfaces from digestive enzymes, blood, spoilage organism and remaining visceral matter	BRINED SALMON	CLEANED SALMON
PRECOOKING	includes the steps of enclosing fish in a pressure vessel, heating the fish under pressure by saturated steam with a temperature of above 101 °C to 132 °C. Until the heat within the fish is sufficient to enable the backbone temperature to reach about 57 ° C. with equilibration, removing the fish from the pressure vessel with a backbone temperature of 29 °C, and equilibrating the heated fish outside of the pressure vessel until the temperature of the backbones of the fish reach about 57°C	CLEANED SALMON	PRECOOKED SALMON
CANNING	Salmon is filled in a can, previously sterilized, in which brine, water or oil is added	PRECOOKED SALMON	CANNED SALMON
CANNED SALMON	the can is sealed airtight and sterilized. The post-sterilized cans are labelled according to the type of fish which is canned		
PACKAGING AND LABELLING	Wrapping products and putting them in boxes; 'labelling' means any words, particulars, trade marks, brand name, pictorial matter or symbol relating to a food and placed on any packaging, document, notice, label, ring or collar accompanying or referring to such food	SALMON PREPARATIONS	PACKED AND LABALED
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets and supermarkets	X	PACKED AND LAB.
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home/at restaurant	X	PACKED AND LAB.
FOOD PREPARATION	Using seafood in food recipes	X	PACKED AND LAB.

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Annex 3.1C. Catalogue of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the Atlantic salmon.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY																				
MATRIX	EGGS		JUVENILE SALMON	SMOLT	SALMON							WHOLE SALMON	GUTTED SALMON				FILLETS			
STEP	BREEDING		JUVENILE SALMON PRODUCING	SMOLT PRODUCING	SALMON FARMING	GRADING	STARVING	CROWDING	CATCHING	TRANSPORT	CHILLING LIVE FISH	STUNNING/KILLING	REFRIGERATION	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILETING-SKINNING	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	PUFA Omega-3 (EPA, DHA), minerals (Iodine, Selenium, Calcium, Iron, Sodium, Posphorus), vitamins (vit. B6, B12, vit A, D, E)		amino acids, PUFA Omega-3, minerals, vitamins, stress indicators (e.g., cortisol in water, blood and muscles, ROS, leukocytes)		stress indicators (e.g., cortisol, ROS, steroid hormones)			fatty acid composition (Omega-3), minerals, vitamins, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA (Thiobarbituric Acid), TVB-N (total volatile base nitrogen) values, freshness index for fish muscle (K-value), organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA (Thiobarbituric Acid), TVB-N (total volatile base nitrogen) values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA (Thiobarbituric Acid), TVB-N (total volatile base nitrogen) values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA (Thiobarbituric Acid), TVB-N (total volatile base nitrogen) values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics								
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	water T, proximate composition, oxygen, light		feed composition, water T, time, oxygen, light condition, stocking density, fish health status, seasonal variation, effect of hormones		t, water T			environment, life cycle, nutritional status, method efficiency	t, T, microorganisms content	method efficiency, t, T	T, t, humidity	t, handling practices efficiency								
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS		chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID), LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, HPLC-MS/MS, UPLC, RIA, ELISA, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, leukocyte count		chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC-MS/MS, UPLC, RIA, ELISA, leukocyte count			chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS), LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, Distillation and Titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests												
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, gonadosomatic index, eggs diameter, oxygen meter, light meter		scale, T sensor, Oxygen Meter, Light Meter, time logger, cameras		time logger, T sensor			logbook	time logger, T sensor, chemical analysis	time logger, logbook	T sensor, hygrometer, time logger	HACCP manual, time logger								

MATRIX	SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)							GUTTED SALMON	FILLETS			SMOKED SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)	VACUUM PACKED SMOKED SALMON	SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)				SALMON CAN	PACKED AND LABELED SALMON				SALMON READY TO EAT
STEP	FREEZING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	PACKAGING AND LABELLING	UNPACKING	THAWING	BEHEADING AND VISCERA REMOVAL	FILETTING	DRY/BRINING SALTING	RINSING	SMOKING	COOLING	SLICING AND CUTTING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	BRINE SALTING	CLEANING	PRECOOKING	CANNING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	TRANSPORT	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	sodium, sodium tripolyphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics			texture, protein denaturated	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	phenols, PUFA Omega-3, organoleptic characteristics	organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	aw, salt	organoleptic characteristics	PUFA Omega-3	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TBA, TVB-N values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics				thermolabile compounds (e.g. vitamins, PUFA omega-3), organoleptic characteristics		
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	T, t, humidity	x	T, t, humidity, integrity of FCM	T, t, handling practices efficiency			t, brine ratio, pH	T, t, handling practices	T, t	T, t	t, handling practices, microorganisms content	integrity of FCM	brine concentration, efficiency of method applied	T, t, techniques applied efficiency, washing water composition	T, t	ingredients added quality, t, microorganisms	T, t, light, microorganisms content, trimethylamine (TMA) content, integrity of FCM	cooking method (T, t)					
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS), LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, Distillation and Titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests													Titration, Drying		visual inspection, non destructive tests	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-MS, GC-FID	chemical analysis: e.g., Titration, HPLC, Kjeldahl distillation, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, visual inspection and non destructive tests				chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-MS, GC-FID, visual inspection	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, hygrometer, time logger	x	visual inspection or non destructive tests	time logger, HACCP manual, visual inspection			pH meter, hygrometer, time logger	time logger, visual inspection, T sensor	time logger, visual inspection	time logger, visual inspection	time logger, HACCP manual, visual inspection	human or computer vision check	time logger, logbook, T sensor	Temperature sensor, time logger, chemical analysis	T sensor, time logger	time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based technique, ELISA, capillary electrophoresis with electrogenerated chemiluminescence (CE-ECL), colorimetric methods	time logger, T sensor						

steps in <i>italics</i> are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the Atlantic salmon.

SAFETY																				
MATRIX	EGGS	JUVENILE SALMON	SMOLT	SALMON								WHOLE SALMON	GUTTED SALMON					FILLETS		
STEP	BREEDING	JUVENILE SALMON PRODUCING	SMOLT PRODUCING	SALMON FARMING	GRADING	STARVING	CROWDING	CATCHING	TRANSPORT	<i>CHILLING LIVE FISH</i>	STUNNING/KILLING	REFRIGERATION	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILETTING-SKINNING		
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical contaminants (e.g., persistent organic pollutants (POPs)); biological contaminants: <i>Listeria Monocytogenes</i> , <i>Piscine Orthoreovirus</i> (PRV), <i>Piscirickettsia salmonis</i> , orthomyxovirus	chemical contaminants: methylmercury; biological contaminants: <i>Piscirickettsia salmonis</i> , orthomyxovirus, microbial status (TVC, coliforms and <i>Staphylococcus</i>), sea lice;					x	x	biological c. <i>Listeria Monocytogenes</i> , <i>Piscine Orthoreovirus</i> (PRV), <i>Piscirickettsia salmonis</i> , orthomyxovirus	chemical contaminants: toxic and potentially toxic elements, phthalates, BPA; biological contaminants: <i>Listeria</i> spp., <i>Vibrio parahaemolyticus</i> (raw fish) <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i> , mesophilic <i>Lactobacilli</i> and <i>Lactococci</i> , reducing sulphite clostrides (SCR), fungi (yeasts and mold), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g. tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine, phthalates); physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone; aw, pH										
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	hygiene procedures efficiency	feed composition, T, pest and disease management efficiency					x	x	cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of food contact material (FCM)										
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: the probability of detection (POD) function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, GC-ECD, HPLC					x	x	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, GC-ECD, HPLC, HPLC/MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, Ion chromatography-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, titration, drying, visual inspection, non destructive test										
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	HACCP manual, logbook (iodophores use), T sensor	HACCP manual, logbook, T sensor					x	x	HACCP manual	HACCP manual, T sensor, time logger										

MATRIX	VARIOUS COMMERCIAL FORMATS					GUTTED SALMON	FILETS			SMOKED SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)			VACUUM PACKED SMOKED SALMON	SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)				SALMON CAN	PACKED AND LABELED SALMON					SALMON READY TO EAT
	FREEZING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	PACKAGING AND LABELLING	UNPACKING	THAWING		BEHEADING AND VISCERA REMOVAL	FILETTINGS	DRY/BRINING SALTING	RINSING	SMOKING	COOLING		SLICING AND CUTTING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	BRINE SALTING	CLEANING		PRECOOKING	CANNING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	TRANSPORT	RETAIL	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical contaminants: toxic and potentially toxic elements, phtalates, BPA; biological contaminants: Listeria spp., Vibrio parahaemolyticus (raw fish) Staphylococcus aureus, Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, reducing sulphite clostrides (SCR), fungi (yeasts and mold), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g. tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine, phtalates); physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone; aw, pH												chemical contaminants: phtalates, BPA; biological contaminants: Listeria spp., Clostridium spp., Vibrio parahaemolyticus (raw fish) Staphylococcus aureus, Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, fungi (yeasts and mold), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g. tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine, phtalates); physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone	chemical contaminants: toxic and potentially toxic elements, phtalates, BPA; biological contaminants: Listeria spp., Clostridium spp., Vibrio parahaemolyticus (raw fish) Staphylococcus aureus, Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, fungi (yeasts and mold), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g. tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine, phtalates); physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone; aw, pH	chemical contaminants: phtalates, BPA; biological contaminants: viruses, bacteria, fungi, parasites, biogenic amines; physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone									
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of food contact material (FCM)												package material, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM	T, t, brine ratio, cleaning and handling practices efficiency	T, t, water quality	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM	ingredients added safety, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM	T, t, packaging atmosphere, icleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM	T, t, humidity, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, refrigeration system control efficiency, integrity of FCM					T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures, integrity of FCM
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, GC-ECD, HPLC, HPLC/MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, Ion chromatography-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, titration, drying, visual inspection, non destructive test												microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based technique, ELISA, ASE, GC-MS/MS, gas chromatography electron capture detection (GC-ECD), HPLC, LC-MS/MS, Ion chromatography-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, Titration, Drying, visual inspection, non destructive test											
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	HACCP manual, T sensor, time logger												HACCP manual	HACCP manual, logbook, T, pH sensor, scale	HACCP manual (handling practices), analysis	T sensor, analysis	time logger, logbook, analysis	HACCP manual, logbook, T sensor, time logger	T ambient sensor, time logger, humidity sensor, light sensor, aroma sensor, HACCP manual, visual inspection					time logger, T sensor

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the Atlantic salmon.

AUTHENTICITY/TRANSPARENCY																				
MATRIX	EGGS		JUVENILE SALMON	SMOLT	SALMON							WHOLE SALMON	GUTTED SALMON				FILLETS			
STEP	BREEDING		JUVENILE SALMON PRODUCING	SMOLT PRODUCING	SALMON FARMING	GRADING	STARVING	CROWDING	CATCHING	TRANSPORT	CHILLING LIVE FISH	STUNNING/KILLING	REFRIGERATION	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILETING-SKINNING	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile					x		x		x				x						
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	climatic conditions		climatic conditions, feed composition			x		x		x				x						
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques, disciplinary of production (for certificated products)					x		x		x				x						
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	disciplinary of the production (for certificate product), logbook, chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, kjeldhal method, Soxhlet extraction technique					x		x		x				x						

MATRIX	VARIOUS COMMERCIAL FORMATS					GUTTED SALMON	FILLETS			SMOKED SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)			VACUUM PACKED SMOKED SALMON	SALMON (VARIOUS FORMATS)				SALMON CAN	PACKED AND LABELED SALMON				SALMON READY TO EAT	
STEP	FREEZING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	PACKAGING AND LABELLING	UNPACKING	THAWING	BEHEADING AND VISCERA REMOVAL	FILETINGS	DRY/BRINING SALTING	RINSING	SMOKING	COOLING	SLICING AND CUTTING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	BRINE SALTING	CLEANING	PRECOOKING	CANNING	PACKAGING-LABELLING	TRANSPORT	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST										x								T, t, lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile	x	T, t, lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile		x		x
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE										x									geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species					x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING										x									chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques, visual inspection					x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING										x									logbook					x

steps in italics are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Annex 3.2A Common sole supply chain.

Annex 3.2B. Steps list of common sole supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs and descriptions of product's typologies.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
CATCHING	Seafood is caught	X	SOLE
CHILLING LIVE FISH	In some slaughter houses farmed fish are chilled alive before slaughtering. It reduce muscle T close to 0°C slows down the microbiological, chemical and biochemical decomposition processes. Farm fish need to be slowly chilled down	SOLE	SOLE CHILLED
STUNNING/KILLING	The animal is first stunned to make it insensible to pain. Death is then induced by various methods that include bleeding, stopping the heart, or preventing access to oxygen. This stages can occur together. Percussive stunning devices are becoming widespread within salmon industry	SOLE CHILLED	SOLE KILLED
REFRIGERATION	Sole is chilled quickly in a cooling tub (at 0°) and kept at low T throughout processing line to slow down the microbiological, chemical and biochemical decomposition processes	SOLE KILLED	WHOLE SOLE
PACK-LABEL FRESH WHOLE SOLE	Sole that has not been canned, smoked or frozen, or has undergone any treatment other than refrigeration		
CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	It is recommended to cut the gills. Is only applicable to medium to large species. Should be bled as soon as possible for a minimum of 20-30 min	WHOLE SOLE	CUTTED SOLE
GUTTING	To prevent autolytic spoilage rather than bacterial spoilage. The gutting of the body cavity, removal of guts and kidney tissue and vacuum suction can be performed in multi-application machines	CUTTED SOLE	GIVEN SOLE
CLEANING	The fish should be washed thoroughly with clean, cold running fresh water or sea water to clean the surfaces from digestive enzymes, blood, spoilage organism and remaining visceral matter	GIVEN SOLE	CLEANED SOLE
SORTING AND GRADING	Standards establish the characteristic and acceptable default which permit fish to be sorted into categories of equal market value	CLEANED SOLE	CLASSIFIED SOLE
BEHEADING	Mechanized or manual process	SOLE CLASSIFIED	GUTTED SOLE
PROCESSING WASTE	Fish residues can be transformed into flour and oil	SOLE RESIDUES	FLOUR AND OIL
FILETTING AND SKINNING	The flesh of a fish has been cut or sliced away from the bone by cutting length wise along one side of the fish parallel to the backbone; skin removal	GUTTED SOLE	FILLET AND/OR SKINNED SOLE
SHARP FREEZING	A method for preservation of foods by rapid freezing until the product core temperature reaches -18 °C. Freezing done in such a way that the zone of maximum crystallization is passed through rapidly and the freezing is complete only when the average temperature reaches -18°C	FILLET AND/OR SKINNED SOLE	FREEZED SOLE
QUICK FREEZING	The freezing process shall be carried out in appropriate equipment in such a way that the range of temperature of maximum crystallization is passed quickly. The quick freezing process shall not be regarded as complete unless and until the product temperature has reached -18°C (0oF) or colder at the thermal centre after thermal stabilization	FILLET AND/OR SKINNED SOLE	FREEZED SOLE
GLAZING	Application of a protective layer of ice formed at the surface of a frozen product by spraying it with, or dipping it into, clean seawater, potable water, or potable water with approved additives, as appropriate	FREEZED SOLE	GLAZED SOLE
ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	Some additives as sodium, sodium triphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates, can be added to maintain the nutritional quality, the shelf-life of fish, and to enhance its colours	SOLE	SOLE (VARIOUS FORMATS)
PACKING AND LABELLING	Wrapping products and putting them in boxes; 'labelling' means any words, particulars, trade marks, brand name, pictorial matter or symbol relating to a food and placed on any packaging, document, notice, label, ring or collar accompanying or referring to such food	FREEZED (AND GLAZED) SOLE	PACKED AND LABELED SOLE
FRESH FILLET	The pieces of meat cut parallel to the backbone of a fish; consist of the right or left lateral part of the fish, provided that the head, the entrails, the fins (dorsal, anal, caudal, ventral, pectoral) and the spines (vertebrae or broad spine, ventral or rib spines, bronchial or stirrups, etc.), and the two side parts are not connected, for example, by the back or stomach of the fish		
FROZEN FILLET	Fish treated by freezing in order to maintain its quality unaltered, by lowering it to -18 °C or more and maintaining the average temperature at -18 °C or more		
COLD STORAGE	Depending on the type of product, specific temperatures are recommended for storage	PACKED AND LAB. SOLE	PACKED AND LAB. SOLE
LANDING	Landing fish at the port	X	PACKED AND LABELED SOLE
TRANSPORT	Vehicle refrigerated or not depending on type of items transported		
AIRLINES	Airlines prefers refrigerant gel pack than ice		
COLD STORAGE	In refrigerators or in freezer		

Steps list (continued) of common sole supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
AUCTION MARKETS	Auction Market is a stage for buyers and sellers where they can trade stocks by making competing bids and offers	X	PACKED AND LABELED SOLE
WHOLESALE OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	Wholesale is the business of selling of goods in large quantities and at low prices to shops and business; Retail distribution is the sale of goods individually or in small quantities to consumers		
LOCAL MARKET/FISHING CO-OPERATIVES	Marketing practices that sell the products in the vicinity of where they are produced		
DISTRIBUTION	Distribution using trucks or cargo through various channels to reach the final consumer. These channels are either retailing companies or other processing companies (for ex. canteen or restaurants)		
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets and supermarkets		
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home/at restaurant		
STORAGE	Cold storage (except for cannery products) at home/ at restaurant/ at canteen		
FOOD PREPARATION	Using seafood in food recipes		FISH READY TO EAT

Annex 3.2C Catalogue of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameter of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the common sole.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY												
MATRIX	WHOLE SOLE					CUTTED SOLE	GIVEN SOLE	CLEANED SOLE	SOLE CLASSIFIED	GUTTED SOLE	FILLET	GLAZED SOLE
STEP	CATCHING	CHILLING LIVE FISH	STUNNING/KILLING	REFRIGERATION (ICING OR REFRIGERATORS)	LANDING AND TRANSPORT	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILLETING-SKINNING	GLAZING (SHARP FREEZING AND QUICK FREEZING)
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	fatty acid composition (Omega-3), minerals, vitamins, texture changes	peroxide value, TMA (Trimethylamine Anhydrous), TBA (Thiobarbituric Acid), TVB-N (total volatile base) and K-value, organoleptic characteristics		peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics					peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	environment, life cycle, nutritional status, method efficiency	T, t, microorganisms content	method efficiency, microorganisms content	T, t, humidity, microorganisms content	T, t, microorganisms content, ice crystal structural damage	t, microorganisms content, handling practices efficiency					T, t, humidity, microorganisms content, ice crystal structural damage	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, distillation and titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests, visual inspections										
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	logbook	time logger, T sensor, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	T sensor, hygrometer, time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	T sensor, time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA, HACCP manual					T sensor, hygrometer, time logger, visual inspection, scale, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	

MATRIX	SOLE (VARIOUS FORMATS)	PACKED SOLE															SOLE READY TO EAT	
STEP	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	PACKAGING AND LABELLING	COLD STORAGE	LANDING	COLD STORAGE	AIRLINES	COLD STORAGE	TRANSPORT	AUCTION MARKETS	WHOLESALE OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	TRANSPORT	LOCAL MARKET	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	sodium, sodium triphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates	peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics	peroxide, TMA, TVB-N, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic characteristics															organoleptic characteristics, thermo-dissociable compounds
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	x	integrity of FCM	T, t, light, microorganisms content, integrity of FCM															cooking method (T, t)
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, distillation and titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests, visual inspections																	
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	x	visual inspection, non destructive tests	T sensor, UV Light Sensor, Time logger, visual inspection, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA															time logger, T sensor

steps in italics are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameter of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the common sole.

SAFETY												
MATRIX	WHOLE SOLE					CUTTED SOLE	GIVEN SOLE	CLEANED SOLE	SOLE CLASSIFIED	GUTTED SOLE	FILLET	GLAZED SOLE
STEP	CATCHING	CHILLING LIVE FISH	STUNNING/KILLING	REFRIGERATION (ICING OR REFRIGERATORS)	LANDING AND TRANSPORT	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILLETING-SKINNING	GLAZING (SHARP FREEZING AND QUICK FREEZING)
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical contaminants (Metil Hg, PBDE, Cadmium, Lead, Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs), microplastics), biological contaminants (e.g., <i>Listeria Monocytogenes</i>)	chemical contaminants: histamine (<i>M. psychrotolerans</i> and <i>P. phosphoreum</i>), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine), toxic and potentially toxic elements; aw, pH, biological contaminants: Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, Clostridium spp. and <i>Listeria</i> spp, fungi (yeasts and mold)										
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	sea water contaminants content, capture zone	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM										
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: probability of detection (POD) function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, gravimetric methods	microbiological analysis: probability of detection (POD) function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, gas chromatography electron capture detection (GC-ECD), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), HPLC/MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, Ion chromatography-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, capillary zone electrophoretic (CZE), Titration, Drying, visual inspection, non destructive test, time logger, pHmeter										
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-MS, solid phase extraction, GPS	T sensor, time logger, hygrometer, logbook, HACCP manual, chemical analysis										

SAFETY																			
MATRIX	SOLE (VARIOUS FORMATS)			PACKED SOLE													SOLE READY TO EAT		
STEP	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES			PACKAGING AND LABELLING	COLD STORAGE	LANDING	COLD STORAGE	AIRLINES	COLD STORAGE	TRANSPORT	AUCTION MARKETS	WHOLESALE OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	TRANSPORT	LOCAL MARKET	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical contaminants: histamine (<i>M. psychrotolerans</i> and <i>P. phosphoreum</i>), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine), toxic and potentially toxic elements; aw, pH, biological contaminants: Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, Clostridium spp. and <i>Listeria</i> spp, fungi (yeasts and mold)			chemical contaminants: heterocyclic amines (HCAs), BPA, phthalates, disinfectants residues; biological contaminants: Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, Clostridium spp. and <i>Listeria</i> spp, fungi (yeasts and mold); histamine (<i>M. psychrotolerans</i> and <i>P. phosphoreum</i>), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine); physical contaminants: foreign matters; aw, pH													chemical contaminants: heterocyclic amines (HCAs), biogenic amines, phthalates, BPA; biological contaminants: bacteria, fungi, parasites; physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone		
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM			T, t, humidity, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, refrigeration system control efficiency, integrity of FCM													T, t, integrity of FCM		
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: probability of detection (POD) function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, gas chromatography electron capture detection (GC-ECD) liquid chromatography (HPLC), HPLC/MS/MS, LC-MS/MS, Ion chromatography-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, capillary zone electrophoretic (CZE), Titration, Drying, visual inspection, non destructive test, time logger, pHmeter																		
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, time logger, hygrometer, logbook, HACCP manual, chemical analysis			HACCP manual, logbook, T sensor, time logger			T ambient sensor, time logger, humidity sensor, light sensor, aroma sensor, HACCP manual										time logger, T sensor		

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steps in <i>italics</i> are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Parameter of Influence monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the common sole.

AUTHENTICITY/ TRANSPARENCY	WHOLE SOLE					CUTTED SOLE	GIVEN SOLE	CLEANED SOLE	SOLE CLASSIFIED	GUTTED SOLE	FILLET	GLAZED SOLE	SOLE (VARIOUS FORMATS)
STEP	CATCHING	CHILLING LIVE FISH	STUNNING /KILLING	REFRIGERATION (ICING OR REFRIGERATORS)	LANDING AND TRANSPORT	CUTTING THE GILLS AND BLEEDING	GUTTING	CLEANING	SORTING AND GRADING	BEHEADING	FILLETING-SKINNING	GLAZING (SHARP FREEZING AND QUICK FREEZING)	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile								x				
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species								x				
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method), DNA-based techniques								x				
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, GPS								x				

MATRIX	PACKED SOLE														SOLE READY TO EAT	
	PACKAGING AND LABELLING	COLD STORAGE	LANDING	COLD STORAGE	AIRLINES	COLD STORAGE	TRANSPORT	AUCTION MARKETS	WHOLESAIL OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	TRANSPORT	LOCAL MARKET	STORAGE	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile						x						lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile	x		x
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species						x						geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species	x		x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	chemical analysis: HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques						x						chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method), DNA-based techniques	x		x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, logbook														x	

steps in italics are optional

violet = off-line laboratory analysis

x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Annex 3.3A. European anchovy supply chain.

Annex 3.3B. Steps list of European anchovy supply chain with their definitions, inputs and outputs and product's typologies descriptions.

STEP	DEFINITION	INPUT	OUTPUT AND MATRIX
CATCHING	Anchovies are caught	X	KILLED ANCHOVY
WASHING	Wash them in running water to remove all the blood and any physical impurities	KILLED ANCHOVIES	CLEANED ANCHOVY
REFRIGERATION	Fish is kept at ~0° C in refrigerators with or without adding crushed ice or in absence of refrigerators covering or alternating the fish with shredded ice	CLEANED ANCHOVY	REFRIGERATED ANCHOVY
LANDING	Landing fish at the port	ANCHOVIES CATCHED	ANCHOVIES BATCHES
LOCAL MARKET/ FISHING CO-OPERATIVES	Marketing practices that sell the products in the vicinity of where they are produced	REFRIG. ANCHOVY	ANCHOVY
FILLETING	Filleting is the neat removal of the flesh of the fish from its skeleton to yield sections of fish flesh free from skin and bone	WHOLE ANCHOVY	FILLET
FREEZING	It is a method for preservation of foods by rapid freezing until the product core temperature reaches -18 ° C. Freezing done in such a way that the zone of maximum crystallization is passed through rapidly and the freezing is complete only when the average temperature reaches -18°C.	ANCHOVY	FREEZED ANCHOVY
DRYING	During the drying process, water is removed from the fish muscle, resulting in decreased water content. The different drying methods include sun drying, solar drying, heat pump drying, freeze-drying, and osmotic dehydration	FILETTED ANCHOVY	DRYIED ANCHOVY
LIGHT DRYING	Anchovies are stored in special containers. The fish is then dried with the aid of a drying centrifuge		
CANNING	The fish is selected and placed in jars of various materials (glass, tin) and various capacity. Then olive or seed oil or other ingredients (like vinegar or spices) are added to cover the entire contents of the jar	FILETTED ANCHOVY	CANNED ANCHOVIES
WASHING IN SALT SOLUTION	The fish is deposited and washed in vats containing brine	REFRIGERATED ANCHOVY	SALTED ANCHOVY
SALTING	For salting the fish is placed in particular tin containers in which layers of salt and layers of fish are alternated	FILETTED ANCHOVY	ANCHOVY IN SALT
CRUSHING	Anchovies are ground and in some cases oil or other ingredients are added	DRYED ANCHOVY	ANCHOVIES PASTE
ANCHOVIES PASTE	Anchovy paste is a mass-produced product, and is sometimes produced using leftover anchovies from anchovy packing facilities that are processed, mixed with additional ingredients, and packaged into tubes		
ANCHOVIES OIL	Anchovies undergo a rapid steam pass to clot proteins and let liquids out of cells (water and oil) and are then mechanically pressed cold to collect raw fish oil		
ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	Some additives as sodium, sodium tripolyphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates, can be added to maintain the nutritional quality, the shelf-life of fish, and to enhance its colours.	ANCHOVY	PROCESSED ANCHOVY
PACKAGING	Depending on the production process, anchovies are packaged in containers of different materials (tin, glass) and various capacity.	PROCESSED ANCHOVY	PACKED ANCH. PREPARATIONS
PROCESSING WASTE	Anchovies residues can be transformed into fishmeal or paste	ANCHOVY RESIDUES	FISHMEAL OR PASTE
STORAGE	Cold storage except for cannery products	X	PACKED ANCH.
TRANSPORT	Vehicle refrigerated or not depending on type of items transported		
AIRLINES	Airlines prefers refrigerant gel pack than ice		
AUCTION MARKETS	Auction Market is a stage for buyers and sellers where they can trade stocks by making competing bids and offers		
WHOLESALE OR RETAIL DISTRIBUTION	Wholesale is the business of selling of goods in large quantities and at low prices to shops and business; Retail distribution is the sale of goods individually or in small quantities to consumers		
LOCAL MARKET/ FISHING CO-OPERATIVES	Marketing practices that sell the products in the vicinity of where they are produced		
DISTRIBUTION	Distribution using trucks or cargo through various channels to reach the final consumer. These channels are either retailing companies or other processing companies (for ex. canteen or restaurants)		
RETAIL	Process that showcases the product for the consumer. This can be in the form of local corner shops or large hypermarkets and supermarkets		
TRANSPORT	Bringing the item purchased at home/at restaurant/ at canteen		
STORAGE	Cold storage (except for cannery products) at home/ at restaurant/ at canteen		
FOOD PREPARATION	Using seafood in food recipes	PACKED AND LAB. ANCHOVY	ANCHOVY READY TO EAT

Annex 3.3C Catalogue of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the European anchovy.

NUTRITIONAL QUALITY		RAW ANCHOVY				PROCESSED ANCHOVY	
MATRIX	CATCHING	WASHING	REFRIGERATION AND FREEZING	LANDING	FILLETING	DRYING	LIGHT DRYING
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	fatty acids (EPA and DHA); vitamins (vit B2, vit PP, vit D, vit A); minerals (iodine, selenium, iron, calcium and phosphorus), texture	texture, odour	peroxide TMA, TBA, TVB values, K-value, organoleptic profile	peroxide, TMA, TVB, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic profile	peroxide, TMA, TVB, TBA values, K-value, Protein hydrolysis and release of ammonia, other free amino acids, volatile compounds, organoleptic profile	peroxide, TMA, TVB, TBA values, K-value	
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	environment, life cycle, nutritional status, method efficiency	T, t, techniques applied efficiency, washing water quality	T, t, techniques applied efficiency, microorganisms content	T, t, microorganisms content	T, t, pH	T, t, techniques efficiency, microorganisms content	
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, Distillation and Titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests					
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	chemical analysis	Temperature sensor, time logger	T sensor, time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	T sensor, time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	T, time logger, pH sensor	T, time and chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	

MATRIX	PROCESSED ANCHOVY				PACKED ANCHOVY						ANCHOVY READY TO EAT		
STEP	CANNING	WASHING IN BRINE	SALTING	CRUSHING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	TRANSPORT	TRANSPORT	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	peroxide, TMA, TVB, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic profile	water activity (aw), salt quality and quantity	homogeneity, texture	sodium, sodium triphosphate (STPP), artificial colouring and polyphosphates	peroxide, TMA, TVB, TBA values, K-value, organoleptic profile						organoleptic profile, thermo-dissociable compounds		
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	t, ingredients added quality, integrity of FCM (microorganisms)	t, T, pH, brine concentration and quality, method applied efficiency	T, t, machinery efficiency (e.g., velocity, intensity)	x	T, t, light, microorganisms content, TMA content, integrity of FCM						cooking method (T, t)		
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., GC, GC-FID, LC-MS/MS, LC/ESI-MS/MS, HPLC, UPLC, FAAS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, FT-NIR spectroscopy, Kjeldahl Distillation Method, Distillation and Titration, freshness testing paper (FTP) and column chromatography, non destructive tests												
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	ingredients list, nutritional facts, time logger, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA	T sensor, time logger, logbook, pH sensor	T sensor, time logger, logbook	x	T sensor, UV Light Sensor, time logger, visual inspection, chemical analysis: DNA-based techniques, ELISA						time logger, T sensor		

steps in italics are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the European anchovy.

SAFETY												
MATRIX	RAW ANCHOVY								PROCESSED			
STEP	CATCHING	WASHING	REFRIGERATION AND FREEZING	LANDING	FILLETING	DRYING	LIGHT DRYING	CANNING	WASHING IN BRINE	SALTING	CRUSHING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	biological contaminants (e.g. Anisakis, Listeria monocytogenes, Escherichia coli, Salmonella), physical contaminants (e.g., microplastics)	chemical contaminants: degradation of ATP in muscles (release of hypoxanthine), protein hydrolysis and release of ammonia, free amino acids and volatile compounds; biological contaminants: E. coli, Salmonella spp., Staphylococci, Enterococci, Listeria monocytogenes, microorganisms of the genus Vibrio	chemical contaminants: histamine (M. psychrotolerans and P. phosphoreum), histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine), toxic and potentially toxic elements; biological contaminants: Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococci, Clostridium spp. and Listeria spp, fungi (yeasts and mold); aw, pH									
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	sea water contaminants content, capture zone	water contaminants content	T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM									
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: probability of detection (POD) function, CFU count, In-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, gravimetric methods	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, gravimetric methods	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, In-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, gravimetric methods, pHmeter									
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-MS, solid phase extraction, GPS	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-MS, solid phase extraction, HACCP manual	HACCP manual, logbook, T and pH sensor, time logger									

MATRIX	PACKED ANCHOVY								ANCHOVY READY TO EAT
STEP	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	TRANSPORT	AIRLINES	DISTRIBUTION	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	chemical contaminants: histamine (<i>M. psychrotolerans</i> and <i>P. phosphoreum</i>); histidine and other biogenic amines (e.g., tyramine, putrescine, cadaverine), toxic and potentially toxic elements; biological contaminants: Enterobacteriaceae, mesophilic Lactobacilli and Lactococchi, Clostridium spp. and Listeria spp, fungi (yeasts and mold); physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone; aw, pH								chemical contaminants: heterocyclic amines (HCAs), biogenic amines, phthalates, BPA; biological contaminants: bacteria, fungi, parasites; physical contaminants: foreign matters, fishbone
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	T, t, humidity, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, refrigeration system control efficiency, integrity of FCM								T, t, cleaning and sanitizing procedures efficiency, integrity of FCM
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	microbiological analysis: POD function, CFU count, in-vitro pathogenicity tests; chemical analysis: e.g., DNA-based techniques, ELISA, Accelerated Solvent Extraction (ASE), GC-MS/MS, AAS, ICP-AES, ICP-MS, gravimetric methods, non destructive tests								
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual	T ambient sensor, time logger, humidity sensor, HACCP manual, logbook							T sensor, time logger, HACCP manual

steps in italics are optional
violet = off-line laboratory analysis
x = not relevant

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

Catalogue (continued) of Parameters of Interest, Parameters of Influence, Parameters of Interest monitoring, Influence parameters monitoring for Nutritional Quality, Safety, Authenticity and Transparency concerning the European anchovy.

AUTHENTICITY/ TRANSPARENCY	RAW ANCHOVY					PROCESSED ANCHOVY				PROCESSED ANCHOVY		
MATRIX	CATCHING	WASHING	REFRIGERATION AND FREEZING	LANDING	FILLETING	DRYING	LIGHT DRYING	CANNING	WASHING IN BRINE	SALTING	CRUSHING	ADDITION OF ADDITIVES
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile		x						x			x
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species		x						x			x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques, logbook											
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	GPS, logbook, disciplinary of the production (for certificate product)		x						x			x

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MATRIX	PACKED FISH								FISH
	PACKAGING AND LABELING	STORAGE	TRANSPORT	AIRLINES	DISTRIBUTION	RETAIL	TRANSPORT	STORAGE	FOOD PREPARATION
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST	lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile			x		lipidic profile, isotopic ratios, genomic and proteomic profile, morphological profile		x	x
PARAMETERS OF INFLUENCE	geo/climatic environment, capture zone (latitude, longitude), species								x
PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING	chemical analysis: e.g., HPLC, GC-FID, GC-MS, HS-SPME-GC-MS, UV/VIS Spectrophotometry, Isotope ratio mass spectrometry, Folin-Ciocalteu method, DNA-based techniques, logbook								x
INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING	logbook								x

steps in italics are optional

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INFLUENCE PARAMETERS: all parameters (techniques, equipment, etc.) refer to supply chain not to analytical procedures

PARAMETERS OF INTEREST MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

INFLUENCE PARAMETERS MONITORING: real-time or off-line analysis

